

InGRID

Integrating expertise in inclusive growth

www.inclusivegrowth.be

Milestone 20.8

METHODOLOGICAL AND DATA INFRASTRUCTURE REPORT FOR THE ELDERLY

Marianna Kopasz

September 2015

This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Programme for Research, Technological Development and Demonstration under Grant Agreement No 312691

This report constitutes Milestone 20.8, for Work Package 20 of the InGRID project.

September 2015

© 2015 – InGRID, Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – project number 312691

General contact: inclusive.growth@kuleuven.be
p.a. InGRID
HIVA - Research Institute for Work and Society
Parkstraat 47 box 5300, 3000 LEUVEN, Belgium

For more information marianna.kopasz@gmail.com

Please refer to this publication as follows:

Kopasz M. (2015), Methodological and data infrastructure report for the elderly, Working paper, Leuven, InGRID project, M20.8.

Information may be quoted provided the source is stated accurately and clearly.

This publication is also available via <http://www.inclusivegrowth.be/project-output>

This publication is part of the InGRID project, this project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Programme for Research, Technical Development and Demonstration under Grant Agreement No 312691.

The information and views set out in this paper are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of life or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

Contents

1.	Aim and context of this report	5
2.	The proposed structure of IPOLIS and the Elderly module	7
3.	Policy context and some initiatives prior to IPOLIS	10
3.1	Policy context	10
3.2	Some initiatives prior to IPOLIS	11
4.	Data infrastructure	14
5.	The selected indicators by domain	17
5.1	Indicators in the domain 'Material living conditions'	17
5.1.1	Poverty	17
5.1.2	Material deprivation	18
5.1.3	Housing	18
5.1.4	Poverty and social exclusion	19
5.2	Indicators in the domain 'Labour market attachment and work-life balance'	21
5.2.1	Labour market attachment	21
5.2.2	Work-life balance	22
5.3	Indicators of the domain 'Education and training'	23
5.3.1	Access to and quality of education	24
5.3.2	Educational achievement	24
5.4	Indicators of the domain 'Health and risk behaviours'	26
5.4.1	Health status	26
5.4.2	Health behaviours	28
5.4.3	Risk behaviours	28
5.5	Indicators of the domain 'Social connectedness and participation'	32
5.5.1	Family and peer relationships	32
5.5.2	Civic participation	33
5.6	Indicators of the domain 'Environmental quality and physical safety'	35
5.6.1	Environmental quality	36
5.6.2	Physical safety	36
6.	Recommendations for improving the monitoring of older people's quality of life	49
6.1	1. Encouraging the extension of monitoring of older people in terms of quality of life domains and components	49
6.2	Extending the monitoring of older people to the "oldest old"	50
6.3	Supporting Member States to participate in SHARE to promote full country coverage in certain QoL domains	51
6.4	Supporting the harmonisation of data infrastructure regarding the QoL of older people	51
	References	52

1. Aim and context of this report

About InGRID

Referring to the increasingly challenging EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the objectives of the [InGRID](#) project are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘poverty and living conditions’ and ‘working conditions and vulnerability’ by improving the transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

InGRID is supported by the European Commission under the 7th Framework Programme.

This report provides a methodological and data infrastructure proposal for the Elderly Module of the Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System (IPOLIS) (Gábos and Kopasz, 2014). As part of the InGRID project, the Poverty and living conditions pillar (see short description in the text box on this page) aims to provide a data infrastructure named IPOLIS to improve the monitoring and analysis of the situation of the most vulnerable population groups in Europe. IPOLIS is conceived to serve as a resource for various user groups (researchers, policy makers at different levels, NGO experts, journalists, students, etc.) to:

- monitor the situation of children, the youth and the elderly in the field of poverty, living conditions and quality of life;
- observe relationships between indicators and to detect cross-country patterns according to selected measures.

Quality of life as the core concept of IPOLIS. The general framework of IPOLIS is outlined in the concept paper for the IPOLIS Database (Gábos and Kopasz 2014, referred hereinafter as Concept paper). This rests on the concept of Quality of Life, which is defined as a multidimensional concept comprising objective measures and people’s perceptions of these factors (economic, social, etc.), that is, subjective measures of objective substances (Joint Research Centre – IPSC 2012: 17). The Quality of Life concept, as proposed in the Concept Paper, includes objective living conditions (including material and non-material aspects, e.g. material deprivation, or long-standing illness), and subjective perceptions about these factors (e.g. inability of making ends meet, or self-reported health status). Accordingly, IPOLIS consists of six quality of life domains: (a) material living conditions; (b) labour market attachment and work-life balance; (c) education and training; (d) health and risk behaviours; (e) social connectedness and civic participation; and (f) environmental

quality and physical safety. The Elderly module, in line with the already completed Child (Gábos and Kopasz 2015) and Youth modules of IPOLIS (Schäfer, Zentarra and Groh-Samberg 2015) follows the general framework of IPOLIS outlined in the Concept Paper.

Incorporating three age groups in a single frame. While the prior quality of life (or well-being) indicator system initiatives generally cover either one specific age group or the population as a whole (Gábos and Kopasz 2014), the specificity of IPOLIS is that it aims to be an indicator system that allows for handling three age groups (children, the youth and the elderly) within a single frame. Therefore, it is important to ensure a coherence of the indicator system at the level of domains, components and subcomponents. At the same time, it is also important to consider that each stage of life cycle has its own characteristics and to pay special attention to age-group specific problems.

Data driven indicator system based mainly on European Statistical System. Considering the above listed aims of IPOLIS, the proposed set of indicators are strongly data driven. Accordingly, the structure of the database as well as the indicator selection process is conditioned by the availability of data. The European Statistical System (ESS) data is given priority in selecting the specific indicators. IPOLIS is planned to cover all EU Member States in the time period of 2004 to 2013 (or the latest year available at the time of data upload to the database). This means that, for the purpose of building IPOLIS only regular data sources are appropriate. This is a difference from the indicator system initiatives prior to IPOLIS, which use data from ad-hoc survey modules too.

The present report aims to:

- provide a full indicator proposal for the elderly portfolio of IPOLIS;
- prepare an indicator fiche for each and every proposed indicator;
- make ready the set-up of the Elderly module of the IPOLIS database (including main indicators as well as breakdowns).

The paper is organised in the following way. In Chapter 2, we briefly present the structure of IPOLIS as outlined in the Concept Paper. Also, we discuss the problems of defining ‘old age’. The policy context of monitoring elderly people’s quality of life and the prior indicator system initiatives are outlined in Chapter 3. In Chapter 4, we take an inventory of the data infrastructure we can use to provide input for the Elderly Module of IPOLIS. Chapter 5, the core chapter of the paper, is devoted to the selection of indicators measuring the different aspects of older adults’ quality of life. In order to select the most appropriate indicators for each domain and component of IPOLIS, we review the potential relevant indicators that meet the criteria of indicator selection laid down in the Context Paper. Finally, Chapter 6 provides recommendations for the improvement of measurement and data infrastructure.

2. The proposed structure of IPOLIS and the Elderly module

In Table 1, we present the proposed structure (domains, components and subcomponents) of IPOLIS as presented in Gábos and Kopasz (2014, 2015). The indicator system incorporates six quality of life domains: material living conditions, labour market attachment and work-life balance, education and training, health and risk behaviours, social connectedness and civic participation, physical environment and safety. These six domains will be supplemented by policy and context indicators.

Table 1. The domains, components and subcomponents of IPOLIS

	Domain	Component	Subcomponent
1.	Material living conditions	1.1 Poverty	a. Extent of poverty b. Depth of poverty c. Persistence of poverty
		1.2 Material deprivation	
		1.3 Housing	a. Overcrowding b. Housing costs c. Housing deprivation
		1.4 Poverty and social exclusion (EU2020)	
2.	Labour market attachment and work-life balance	2.1 Labour market attachment	a. Employment b. Precarious employment c. Self-employment d. Unemployment e. Labour market attachment of hhs
		2.2 Work-life balance	a. Work and leisure b. Work and care
3.	Education and training	3.1 Access to and quality of education	a. Early childhood education b. Educational attainment c. Lifelong learning
		3.2 Educational achievement	a. Achievement in basic skills b. Early school leaving
4.	Health and risk behaviours	4.1 Health status	a. Objective health status b. Subjective health status
		4.2 Health behaviours	a. Physical activity b. Obesity
		4.3 Risk behaviours	a. Smoking b. Alcohol consumption c. Illicit drugs d. Teenage births e. Psychological distress f. Suicide
5.	Social connectedness and CIVIC participation	5.1 Family and peer relationships	a. Family relationships b. Peer relationships
		5.2 Civic participation	a. Voting/Voter turnout b. Volunteering and group membership c. Internet use
6.	Environmental quality and physical safety	6.1 Environmental quality	
		6.2 Physical safety	

Source Gábos & Kopasz, 2014; 2015

This paper addresses the Elderly module of IPOLIS. Thus, the first issue to be discussed is the definition of *old age*. The United Nations uses 60 years to refer to older people. This line, which divides younger and older cohorts of a population, is also used by demographers. However, in many developed countries, the age of 65 is used as a reference point for older persons as this is often the age at which persons become eligible for old-age social security benefits. So, there is no exact definition of *old* as this concept has different meanings in different societies. Defining *old* is further challenged by the changing average lifespan of human beings (UNFPA 2012:20).

There are other definitions of *old* that go beyond chronological age. As a social construct, old age is often associated with a change of social roles and activities, for example, becoming a grandparent or a pensioner. Older persons often define old age as a stage at which functional, mental and physical capacity is declining and people are more prone to disease or disabilities (UNFPA 2012: 20).

Older persons are a highly diverse population group. Gerontologists have recognised the very different conditions that people experience as they grow older within the years defined as old age. In developed countries, most people in their 60s and early 70s are still fit, active, and able to care for themselves (Berk 2013). However, after 75, they will become increasingly frail, a condition marked by serious mental and physical debilitation (Torpy 2006). Therefore, rather than lumping together all people who have been defined as old, some gerontologists have defined sub-groups. One study distinguishes the young-old (65 to 74), the middle-old (75–84), and the oldest-old (85+) (Zizza et al. 2009).

A report by the European Commission titled ‘Active ageing and solidarity between generations’ also states that there is no recognised statistical definition of *old* or *older* (European Commission 2012: 12). A Eurobarometer survey (Special Eurobarometer No. 378) conducted in 2011 asked interviewees (aged 15 and above within the EU-27) at what age people can be considered ‘old’ – the average of the answers given was 63.9 years. Only one in six (16%) of the persons interviewed described themselves as being ‘old’ (European Commission 2012: 12).

The picture of ageing across the EU is further complicated by issues, such as:

- administrative differences: for example, a variety of retirement ages across the EU;
- demographic differences: for example, different observed patterns in life expectancy between countries;
- subjective variations: for example, differences of opinion with respect to the quality of life experienced by older persons (European Commission 2012: 12).

In addition, looking at the operational definitions of old age used by prior indicator system initiatives (see in more detail in Chapter 3) we find marked differences. For example, the Active Ageing Index (Zaidi et al. 2013) for the most part includes indicators for those aged 55+, while the SCL/PRB Index (Kaneda et al. 2011) defines old age as 65+, including two sub-groups: 65-74 and 75+.¹ These differences, however, can be explained to some extent by the differing research goals, i.e. the Active Ageing Index places the ageing process itself in the focus.

From the viewpoint of statistical analysis, the upper age limit of the age group is also problematic. The reason for this is that surveys generally cover the population living in private households, while a significant part of the ‘oldest old’ lives in communal establishments (e.g. old-age homes, long term care facilities, etc.). Although, internationally comparable data are relatively old, it can be clearly seen that the proportion of those living in communal establishments may be quite high in some Member States, e.g. about one in four men and one in three women aged 85 and over in Sweden lived in communal establishments in 2000/01 (Tomassini et al. 2004). In the light of this, it would be reasonable to determine an upper age limit for an operational definition the age group. However, in

¹ Although, the report discusses results for the 65-74 and the 75+ populations, to control for differences in age structure, the SCL/PRB Index measures the well-being of older people in three age groups (50-64, 65-74 and 75+) (Kaneda et al. 2011).

practice, indicators for measuring the quality of life of elderly people are often disseminated without an upper age limit, e.g. for the age groups 60+, 65+, 75+.

Considering that IPOLIS places vulnerable groups in the focus, old age is defined as 65+. In some fields of quality of life, however, it may be reasonable to diverge from this definition – these are the fields of life in which people typically become vulnerable before they turn 65 (e.g. in the domains ‘labour market attachment and work-life balance’ and ‘health and risk behaviours’). Because of the above mentioned potential problem caused by the significant proportion of those living in communal establishments among the ‘oldest old’ (85+), in all cases where it is possible, we define the indicators for the age group with an upper age limit of 84 (or below that).

3. Policy context and some initiatives prior to IPOLIS

3.1 Policy context

The EU has recognised the importance of the ageing challenge for many years and has developed policy in several areas. From the perspective of this report, the designation of 2012 as the European Year for Active Ageing and Solidarity between Generations on 23 September 2011 was an important step in the policy process². In what follows, we first briefly review the antecedents to this.

- 1991: UN Principles for Older Persons³ were adopted by the UN General Assembly. This encourages governments to incorporate the following principles into their national programmes:
 - Independence
 - Participation
 - Care
 - Self-fulfilment
 - Dignity.
- 2002: The Madrid International Plan of Action on Ageing (MIPAA) and its Regional Implementation Strategy (RIS) were adopted at the United Nations Second World Assembly on Ageing held in Madrid in 2002 and subsequently, the General Assembly endorsed the Plan on December 2002. The MIPAA put population ageing at the centre of the development agenda. The Madrid Plan and its Political Declaration set out a comprehensive agenda with core recommendations grouped under the priority directions of
 - older persons and development,
 - advancing health and well-being into old age, and
 - ensuring enabling and supportive environments.
- 2008: The United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) Working Group on Ageing was established as an intergovernmental body reporting to the UNECE Executive Committee. It facilitates and monitors implementation of the international policy framework on ageing as set out in the MIPAA and its RIS.
- 2008: The European Commission's Renewed Social Agenda set out 'Improving the quality of life and the inclusion of the elderly' as a priority area of action. Furthermore, the elderly was identified as one of the most disadvantage groups under the 'Fight against poverty and social exclusion' priority area of action.
- 2012: The EU designated 2012 as the European Year for Active Ageing and Solidarity between Generations (EY2012)⁴. In this context, Guiding Principles for the EY2012 were elaborated by the Social Protection Committee and the Employment Committee. Each of the 19 guiding principles relates to one of the three dimensions of active ageing promoted during the European Year:
 - employment,
 - social participation, and
 - independent living.

2 <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32011D0940&from=EN>

3 <http://www.un.org/documents/ga/res/46/a46r091.htm>

4 The ex-post valuation of the EY2012 is not yet available at the time of preparing this report.

The Active Ageing Index (AAI) was developed in the context of EY2012 to assess the untapped potential of older people. The AAI is a product of a joint project undertaken by the European Commission DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion together with the UNECE and the European Centre for Social Welfare Policy and Research in Vienna. The index measures the extent to which older people can realize their full potential in terms of employment, participation in social and cultural life and independent living. It also measures the extent to which the environment they live in enables seniors to lead an active life⁵.

- 2012: The UNECE Ministerial Conference on Ageing, held in Vienna, concluded with the adoption of the Ministerial Declaration ‘Ensuring a society for all ages: promoting quality of life and active ageing’ which outlined priority directions for the third cycle (2012-2017) of implementation of the MIPAA in the UNECE region.

3.2 Some initiatives prior to IPOLIS

There are few prior international efforts related to monitoring the quality of life or well-being of older people. Within the EU, the Active Ageing Index project stands out as an important exception. Outside Europe, the index constructed by the Stanford Center on Longevity and the Population Reference Bureau, henceforth the SCL/PRB Index, is worth mentioning. Besides these, a global index has been developed recently by HelpAge International, the so-called ‘Global AgeWatch’.

The Active Ageing Index

The conceptual framework for Active Ageing Index is different from that of IPOLIS. According to the definition adopted for the Active Ageing Index, “active ageing refers to the situation where people continue to participate in the formal labour market as well as engage in other unpaid productive activities (such as care provision to family members and volunteering) and live healthy, independent and secure lives as they age” (Zaidi et al. 2013: 6). The Active Ageing Index covers four domains, of which the first three are drawn from the strands of the 2012 European Year of Active Ageing and Solidarity between Generations (EY2012) and represent actual experiences of active ageing. These are: employment, participation in society, independent, healthy and secure living. Capacity and enabling environment for active ageing, included as a fourth domain, serves a foundation of the first three domains, and is inspired by Sen’s capability focussed conceptual framework (Zaidi et al. 2013: 7). That is, the index measures the extent to which older people can realize their full potential in terms of employment, participation in social and cultural life and independent living. It also measures the extent to which the environment they live in enables seniors to lead an active life. The Active Ageing Index is based on data primarily from three surveys: EU-SILC, EU-LFS and EQLS.

⁵ <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?langId=en&catId=89&newsId=1837&furtherNews=yes>

Figure 1. Domains and indicators of the Active Ageing Index

Note. *Financial security aspects are captured by three different indicators: (1) Relative median income of 65+ relative to those aged below 65 (2) No poverty risk for older persons and (3) No severe material deprivation rate.

Source Zaidi et al., 2013

The SCL/PRB Index

The SCL/PRB Index of Well-Being in Older Populations was created by the Population Reference Bureau (PRB) and the Global Aging Program at the Stanford Center on Longevity (SCL). After a review of a comprehensive set of well-being indicators for countries across the world, the research team focused on outcome indicators for which comparable data were available on 12 study countries at similar levels of development: 10 EU Member States, Switzerland and the United States. The SCL/PRB Index is based almost entirely on data from surveys of non-institutionalized populations conducted between 2004 and 2006, the Health and Retirement Surveys (HRS) in the United States and the Study of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE). The index summarizes 12 key indicators of well-being in old age across four domains - material, physical, social, and emotional well-being. All but one of the 12 underlying indicators measures an outcome (the exception is the indicator denoting the percentage of those not obese). The resulting index provides a user-friendly measure that summarizes multiple dimensions of elderly well-being. The report on the SCL/PRB Index discusses results for the 65-74 and 75+ populations. However, to control for differences in age structure across countries, the index measures the well-being of older populations in three age groups (50-64, 65-74 and 75+) (Kaneda et al. 2011).

The Global AgeWatch Index⁶

The Global AgeWatch Index has been developed and constructed by HelpAge International from international data sets drawn from the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs,

⁶ <http://www.helpage.org/global-agemwatch/>

the World Bank, World Health Organization, International Labour Organization, UNESCO and the Gallup World Poll. The Global AgeWatch Index makes international comparisons of quality of life in older age possible. At this stage, 96 countries are included because of current data limitations. The index is inspired by the examples of the Human Development Index as well as the Active Ageing Index. It aims to capture the multidimensional nature of the quality of life and wellbeing of older people, and to provide a means by which to measure performance. The index is based on 13 indicators for the four key domains of Income security, Health status, Capability, and Enabling environment.

4. Data infrastructure

IPOLIS is planned to cover all EU Member States in the time period of 2004 to 2013 (or the latest year available at the time of data upload to the database). This means that comparability across countries, timeliness and regularity of data are very important factors in the choice of datasets.

For the Elderly module of IPOLIS, the EU-SILC (Survey of Income and Living Conditions) and the EU-LFS (the European Union Labour Force Survey) are the prime datasets. Similarly to the EU-LFS, the EQLS (European Quality of Life Survey) and the ESS (European Social Survey) are also adult population surveys. While EQLS has better country coverage (including all the EU-27 Member States) than the ESS (missing countries vary from wave to wave), the latter has the advantage of more frequent periodicity. The EHIS (European Health Interview Survey) is another important data source for the health-related indicators of IPOLIS. While the first wave of EHIS was conducted only in 17 Member States, the 2014 second wave covers all Member States⁷. At the time of preparing this report, only data from the first wave are available. We note, however, that EHIS is given an important role in providing data for European Core Health Indicators (ECHI)⁸. Out of a complete list of 88 European Core Health Indicators, currently there are over 50 health indicators for which data is readily available and reasonably comparable. In addition to these data sources, another supplementary data source for IPOLIS is the Community Survey on ICT usage. Conducted since 2002, this collects data on the use of information and communication technologies (ICT), the internet, e-government and electronic skills in households and by individuals (aged 16 to 74).

Finally, the SHARE (Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement) is the only survey that is conducted exclusively on the older people (50+). This provides information, among others, on health status, health behaviours, risk behaviours, social connectedness and civic participation. The number of participating countries varies from wave to wave. In wave 4 (the last one from which data are available), 16 European countries (15 Member States) participated. (To our knowledge, the number of participating countries in the current wave 5 is 20). Due to the relatively weak coverage of this survey, we decided not to use data from SHARE.

⁷ The EHIS operates under a framework Regulation of the Council and the Parliament (Regulation (EC) No 1338/2008) and the Commission Regulation (EU) No 141/2013 implementing Regulation (EC) No 1338/2008.

⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/health/indicators/docs/echi_shortlist_by_policy_area_en.pdf

Table 2. Overview of data sources for the Elderly module of IPOLIS

Data source	ESS status	Age coverage	Time coverage, periodicity	Country coverage	Domains/components/subcomponents
EU-SILC Statistics on Income and Living Conditions	Part of the ESS	Total population living in private households	2003-, yearly	EU-28, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey	Poverty, material deprivation, housing, health status, family relationships, environmental quality and physical safety
EU-LFS Labour Force Survey	Part of the ESS	Individuals aged 15+ living in private households	1983-, yearly	EU-28, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland	Labour market attachment, access to and quality of education
EHIS European Health Interview Survey	Part of the ESS	All people aged 15+ living in private households. Some countries included also people living in institutions like homes for elderly.	EHIS 1: 2006-2009 EHIS 2: 2013-2015 EHIS 3: 2019, and subsequently every five years	EHIS 1: EU-17, Turkey EHIS 2: EU-28	Health and risk behaviours
ICT ICT usage in households and by individuals	Part of the ESS	Individuals aged 16 to 74	2002-, yearly	EU-28, Iceland, Norway, Macedonia, Serbia, Turkey	Educational achievement, civic participation
EQLS European Quality of Life Survey	Not part of the ESS	Individuals aged 18+ living in private households	EQLS 1: 2003 EQLS 2: 2007-2008 EQLS 3: 2011-2012	EQLS 1: EU-27 and Turkey EQLS 2: EU-27, Croatia, FYR Macedonia, Turkey, Norway EQLS 3: EU-27, Croatia, Iceland, FYR Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Turkey, Kosovo.	Social connectedness and civic participation, environment and physical safety

Data source	ESS status	Age coverage	Time coverage, periodicity	Country coverage	Domains/components/subcomponents
ESS European Social Survey	Not part of the ESS	Individuals aged 15+ living in private household	2001-, every two years	The number of participating EU countries varies from wave to wave. In Round 7: EU-19 and non-EU countries	Social connectedness and civic participation, physical safety
SHARE Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe	Not part of the ESS	Individuals aged 50+	2004-, approximately every two years	SHARE 1: EU-10 SHARE 2: EU-13 SHARE 3: EU-13 SHARE 4: EU-15	Not used for IPOLIS because of the relatively weak country coverage

5. The selected indicators by domain

This chapter is aimed to provide methodological underpinnings of the selection of indicators measuring the different aspects of older people's quality of life. The general criteria applied in the selection of indicators were discussed in the Concept Paper (Gábos and Kopasz 2014). The present chapter, which is the core of this report, is organised by domains and components/subcomponents of IPOLIS (see Chapter 2 for the detailed structure of IPOLIS). Only those components/subcomponents of IPOLIS are discussed here which are relevant for older adults. We review the potential indicators for each domain and component/subcomponent and the data sources that can be used. In case of each domain a table summarizes the indicators used by the Social OMC and the indices of quality of life for measuring the components and subcomponents. Out of the above reviewed indices, the Active Ageing Index is the most important in an EU context, but we also include the SCL/PRB Index in the survey.

5.1 Indicators in the domain 'Material living conditions'

5.1.1 Poverty

The domain 'Material living conditions' consists of four main components: poverty, material deprivation, housing and poverty and social exclusion. In selecting the indicators for the first component 'poverty', we used the indicator portfolios provided by the Social OMC as a starting point. All indicators of poverty we propose are part of either the Overarching Portfolio or one of the thematic portfolios of the Social OMC. We discuss poverty indicators along the three subcomponents of 'poverty': the extent, the depth or intensity, and the persistence of poverty.

The 'extent of poverty' subcomponent of the Elderly module of IPOLIS is represented by two indicators: the 'at-risk-of-poverty rate of elderly people (65+)' and the 'at-risk-of-poverty rate of elderly people (65+) anchored at a fix moment in time (2005)'. The 'at-risk-of-poverty rate' is the leading indicator of the relative income poverty concept and a primary indicator in the Overarching Portfolio of the Social OMC. The Pensions Portfolio of the Social OMC⁹ (or more exactly, the adequate pensions strand) includes the 'at-risk-of poverty rate of elderly people' (65+ as primary indicator and 60+, 75+ as secondary indicator). This measure provides a key indication of the capacity of pension systems to provide adequate income to older people. (We note that this indicator is complemented by the 'at-risk-of poverty rate of pensioners', which is a secondary indicator in the adequate pensions strand of the Pensions Portfolio). The 'at-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fix moment in time (2005)' is a primary indicator in the Overarching Portfolio of the Social OMC¹⁰. This indicator represents the absolute poverty concept, as it is defined as the share of persons aged 65+ with an equivalised disposable income below the at-risk-of poverty threshold calculated in survey year 2005, up-rated by inflation over the years (no further age breakdown is provided for elderly people).

⁹ The Pensions strand of the Social OMC is governed by three main objectives - adequate pensions, sustainable pensions and modernised pensions - and its indicator portfolio is structured along these objectives.

¹⁰ However, it is indicated that it would possibly be replaced or supplemented in future by material deprivation or consistent poverty indicators.

In IPOLIS, the ‘depth of poverty’ subcomponent is represented by the ‘relative median at-risk-of-poverty gap of elderly people for 65+ and 75+’. This indicator is included in the Overarching Portfolio and in the Pensions Portfolio of the Social OMC. It is defined as the difference between the median equivalised income of persons aged 65+ or 75+ below the at-risk-of poverty threshold and the threshold itself, expressed as a percentage of the at-risk-of poverty threshold.

In IPOLIS, we measure the ‘persistence of poverty’ subcomponent using the ‘persistent at risk-of-poverty rate of elderly people (65+)’. This indicator is included in the Social Inclusion Portfolio the Social OMC. The ‘persistent at risk-of-poverty rate of elderly people’ is defined as the share of persons with an equivalised income below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold in the current year and in at least two of the preceding three years. The source of all poverty indicators selected for the Elderly module in IPOLIS is the EU-SILC database. Where it is possible, we disaggregate the indicators by sex, age, and household type. We use a simplified household type variable having three categories: (a) households with one adult aged 65 years or over, (b) households with two adults, at least one aged 65 years or over, (c) other households.

5.1.2 Material deprivation

While risk of poverty is based on a relative poverty definition, material deprivation provides a necessary complementary view, based on objective and absolute criteria.¹¹ Material deprivation refers to the lack of material goods, financial strain and the inability of individuals to live a decent life (Boarini and d’Ercole 2006). In general, measures of material deprivation are composite indices that cover more than one dimension (e.g. financial strain, lack of durables, in some cases even housing deprivation) and consist of several individual items.

Both the Social OMC and the Active Ageing Index contain indicators for measuring material deprivation. The Social Inclusion Portfolio of the Social OMC includes the ‘material deprivation rate’ (as primary indicator) and the ‘depth of material deprivation’ (as secondary indicator and with no age breakdowns). The AAI usually prefers a ‘positive’ formulation of indicators, and uses the indicator ‘no severe material deprivation’, calculated for those aged 65+.

To measure the ‘material deprivation’ component of IPOLIS, we have chosen two indicators. The first is the ‘severe material deprivation rate of elderly people (65+)’, which measures the proportion of older adults living in households being unable to afford (enforced inability) at least four items among the following nine: i) to pay their rent, mortgage or utility bills; to keep their home adequately warm; to face unexpected expenses; to eat meat or proteins regularly; to go on holiday; to have a television set; to have a washing machine; to have a car; to have a telephone.¹² This indicator is part of the EU2020 fight against poverty and social exclusion measure. The second indicator we have chosen is the ‘inability of making ends meet’. This measure is a subjective evaluation of the household’s financial situation. The indicator informs on the proportion of persons in the total population finding it quite or very difficult to get by financially. Both indicators of material deprivation can be derived from the EU-SILC. In the Elderly module of IPOLIS, the indicator of ‘material deprivation’ is disaggregated by household type, sex and age (65-74, 75+), while ‘inability of making ends meet’ is disaggregated by household type and poverty status.

5.1.3 Housing

Housing conditions have an important impact on quality of life. Low housing quality is associated with lower well-being and psychological stress (Abdallah and Stoll 2012). Therefore, indicators

11 http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Quality_of_life_indicators_-_material_living_conditions#Making_ends_meet.2C_a_subjective_indicator_of_poverty

12 The current material deprivation indicator is expected to be replaced by a new one which consists of 13 items (six are common to the current 9-item indicator and seven are new) proposed by Guio, Gordon and Marlier (2012).

measuring housing conditions are a necessary complement to material deprivation when assessing material conditions. An ideal set of housing indicators provides information about both the physical characteristics (quality) of the dwelling and the broader environmental characteristics of the area where the dwelling is located.

The Social OMC contains no primary indicator in the field of housing, but notes that further work, including further improvement of the quality of data is needed before a primary indicator can be identified. Two secondary indicators and two context indicators, however, have been adopted. The secondary indicators, both included in the Social Inclusion Portfolio, are 'housing costs' (or more precisely, housing cost overburden) and 'overcrowding'. One of the context indicators is 'housing deprivation by item' and the other is 'share of housing costs in total disposable household income'.

For assessing housing conditions of elderly people in IPOLIS, we have chosen three indicators, representing the three subcomponents: the 'overcrowding rate (65+)', the 'housing cost overburden rate (65+)' and the 'severe housing deprivation rate (65+)' as indicators of housing. The 'housing cost overburden rate' is defined as the percentage of the population living in a household where total housing costs (net of housing allowances) represent more than 40% of the total disposable household income (net of housing allowances). The 'overcrowding rate' shows the percentage of the population living in an overcrowded household. A person is considered as living in an overcrowded household if the household does not have at its disposal a minimum number of rooms equal to: one room for the household; one room per couple in the household; one room for each single person aged 18 or more; one room per pair of single people of the same gender between 12 and 17 years of age; one room for each single person between 12 and 17 years of age and not included in the previous category; one room per pair of children under 12 years of age. Finally, 'severe housing deprivation' is defined as the percentage of the population living in the dwelling considered as overcrowded (see above), while also exhibiting at least one of the housing deprivation measures. The following housing deprivation items are considered: leaking roof, damp walls/floors/foundations, or rot in window frames or floors; no bath or shower in the dwelling; no indoor flushing toilet for the sole use of the household; dwelling too dark. The source of indicators on housing is the EU-SILC.

Both the overcrowding rate and the severe housing deprivation rate inform about the physical characteristics of the dwelling. However, the housing environment is also an important element of measuring housing conditions. Some characteristics of the residential area, for example crime, vandalism, environmental pollution and grime, are captured by indicators (and will be discussed under the domain 'Environmental quality and physical safety'). However, we lack regular indicators (and the underlying data) on the physical accessibility of basic services (e.g. public transport, food shop, GP, etc.), which is essential for the elderly to live an independent life and actively participate in society. The EU-SILC 2007 contained a special module on Housing, including questions about the accessibility of public transport, grocery services, primary health care services, etc., but these have not become part of the core questionnaire.

For the Elderly module of IPOLIS, we disaggregate the housing indicators by household type, sex and poverty status (i.e. income situation in relation to the risk of poverty threshold), where it makes sense and is possible.

5.1.4 Poverty and social exclusion

Finally, the fourth component of this domain is represented by a single measure 'at risk of poverty or social exclusion of elderly people (65+)'. This is one of the headline indicators of the Europe 2020 strategy. An individual is considered to be at risk of poverty or social exclusion if he or she is at-risk-of-poverty, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity.

Table 3. Material living conditions

Components and subcomponents	SOCIAL OMC	ACTIVE AGEING INDEX	SCL/PRB INDEX	IPOLIS
Poverty				
Extent of poverty	At-risk-of poverty rate 65+ (OP, PP) At risk-of-poverty rate of elderly people 60+ and 75+ (PP) At-risk-of poverty rate anchored at a fixed moment in time (2005) 65+ (OP)	Percentage of people aged 65+ who are not at risk of poverty	Percentage of people not in absolute poverty (65+)	At-risk-of-poverty rate of elderly people (65+) At-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fix moment in time (2005) (65+)
Depth of poverty	Relative median poverty risk gap 65+ (OP) Poverty gap by age brackets 65+ and 75+ (PP)	no	no	Relative median poverty gap (65+)
Persistency of poverty	Persistent at-risk-of poverty rate 65+ (SIP)	no	no	Persistent at-risk-of poverty rate (65+)
Material deprivation				
	Material deprivation rate 65+ (SIP)	Percentage of people aged 65+ who are not severely materially deprived	no	Severe material deprivation rate of elderly people (65+) Inability to make ends meet (65+)
Housing				
Overcrowding	Overcrowding rate (secondary indicator in SIP)	no	no	Overcrowding rate (65+)
Housing costs	Housing cost overburden rate (secondary indicator in SIP); Share of housing costs in total disposable household income (context indicator in SIP)	no	no	Housing cost overburden rate (65+)
Housing deprivation	Housing deprivation (context indicator in SIP)	no	no	Severe housing deprivation rate (65+)
Poverty and social exclusion (EU2020)				
At risk of poverty or social exclusion				At risk of poverty or social exclusion of elderly people (65+)

5.2 Indicators in the domain 'Labour market attachment and work-life balance'

Before discussing the indicators on labour market attachment of older workers, we have to define the concepts of 'prime age worker' and 'older worker'. Different research goals may require different conceptualizations. Thus, similarly to the case with the definition of 'old age', the definition of older worker cannot be independent of the aim of research. For the purpose of this report, we decided to define prime age workers as those between 25 and 54, and older workers are those between 55 and 64. This is in line with the definition of old age workers used in the Social OMC and in the employment policy in relation to older workers in the EU. Specifically, in 2001, the Stockholm European Council set a target that, by 2010, at least half of the EU population aged 55-64 should be in employment. We note, however, that there is no consensus on the conceptualization of older workers. Another common practice is that older workers are defined as persons aged 50 and over.

5.2.1 Labour market attachment

Work provides an important way in which older people remain socially active. Promoting active ageing in employment is both an essential part of the Active Ageing Agenda and a key element of achieving Europe's economic and social goals for the future. The Europe 2020 strategy has set an EU employment rate target of 75% of women and men aged 20-64 by 2020. To achieve this rate, the Commission is encouraging Member States to implement active ageing policies that both discourage the use of early retirement schemes and aim at favouring employment retention and the reintegration of older workers.

In the Elderly module of IPOLIS, the domain 'labour market attachment and work-life balance', as its name suggests, is divided into two components: labour market attachment and work-life balance. The former component covers four subcomponents: employment, precarious employment, self-employment, unemployment and labour market attachment of households.

In order to assess the employment situation of older workers, we have chosen the 'employment rate of elderly people'. This is included in the Active Ageing Index (for four age groups: 55-59, 60-64, 65-69 and 70-74) and also in the Overarching Portfolio provided by the Social OMC (55-59 and 60-64). In IPOLIS, in line with the Active Ageing Agenda, the following age brackets will be used for the employment rates of elderly people: 55-59, 60-64, 65-69 and 70-74.

The second subcomponent is 'precarious employment'. Precarious work is non-standard employment that is characterized by low wages, few benefits, the absence of collective representation and little job security (Fudge and Owens 2006:12). There is growing recognition that specific groups of workers are likely to be particularly vulnerable to low pay and job loss as a result of the increasing trend towards flexible working (Barrett and Sargeant 2008). Although, there is evidence that a substantial number of older workers are in precarious work, older workers are one group who have not received particular attention as vulnerable workers (Sargeant and Frazer 2009). Precarious work tends to be associated with the following forms of employment: part-time employment, self-employment, fixed-term work, temporary work, on-call work, home working and telecommuting. These forms are united more by their divergence from the standard employment relationship (full time, indeterminate work with a single employer) than by any common features (ibid).

In the Elderly module of IPOLIS, 'precarious employment' is measured with the indicator of 'involuntary part-time employment'. Since part-time work is not perceived automatically being precarious (see McKay et al. 2012: 6), we have chosen the indicator of 'involuntary part-time employment'. This refers to those who declare that they work part-time because they are unable to find full-time work. Besides being an indicator of precarious employment, involuntary part-time employment measures one aspect of underemployment. If people work fewer hours than they would

like to, this has implications for their opportunities to earn income, interact socially and shape their identity, all of which impinge on their quality of life.¹³

The indicator ‘involuntary part time employment’ is defined as percentage of total part-time employment. This is calculated based on LFS data. In the majority of Member States, the proportion of involuntary part-time workers is higher among men than among women. This is not surprising, given that women are more likely to have to combine work and family obligations, and thus to ‘prefer’ working part-time. However, this is not the case in all Member States. Involuntary part-time employment is less prevalent among older employees (aged 50-74) than among those aged 15-24 and 25-49. It is important to note, however, that the proportion of the population working part-time is so small in some countries that the figures are unreliable¹⁴.

The Youth module of IPOLIS includes another indicator for measuring precarious employment: ‘temporary employment’. Temporary work is less prevalent among older employees (50-74) than among those aged 25-49, and especially than those aged 15-24 (the very high percentage of the latter age class is due to the fact that many of them have temporary contract because they are in apprenticeships). Since the number of those being temporary employed among older employees is very small in a couple of Member States (below 5,000 persons), we decided not to include an indicator on temporary employment in the Elderly module of IPOLIS.

Although, self-employment is usually considered as form of precarious employment, it constitutes a separate subcomponent in IPOLIS. The rationale behind this is that the definition of the self-employed embraces people who work alone (the largest share) as well as entrepreneurs who own a business that has employees. However, the former group (i.e. the own-account self-employed) is in a more precarious position than the latter (i.e. the self-employed employers) (Fudge et al. 2002). Furthermore, self-employment has long been considered a way for workers to take control of their work-life balance, allowing room for greater flexibility, autonomy and creativity in the way individuals work (Hatfield 2015:27). Finally, self-employment is often seen by policymakers as a way to create new opportunities for those seeking employment. Based on these, we argue that self-employment can be considered as a measure of entrepreneurship as much as a measure of precarious work. In IPOLIS, the ‘self-employment’ subcomponent is represented by the self-employment rate, that is the proportion of self-employment (55-64) in total employment. Data show that the self-employment rate of older workers is higher than for other age-groups. According to 2013 data, only 3 per cent of European self-employed workers are aged 15–24, compared with 42 per cent who are over the age of 50, and 56 per cent aged 25–49. Older workers tend to have more experience and higher levels of human capital, as well as larger capital reserves and better access to credit with which to start a business (Hatfield 2015: 13).

The ‘unemployment’ subcomponent includes the unemployment rate of older workers (55-74). The unemployment rate is defined as the ratio of the unemployed to the labour force. Unemployment refers thus to jobless persons who chose to be active or in the labour force. The employment rate on the other hand is defined as the ratio of the employed to the persons under working age. Thus, the measure of unemployment provides a better link to well-being than the measure of employment (Eurostat 2010).

5.2.2 Work-life balance

The component ‘work-life balance’ seems to be less relevant for the Elderly module of IPOLIS than for the Youth module. It covers two subcomponents: ‘work and leisure’ and ‘work and care’. In the Youth module of IPOLIS, the balance between work and leisure is assessed using the indicator of

13 http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Quality_of_life_indicators_-_productive_or_main_activity#Involuntary_part-time_employment.C2.A0

14 http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Quality_of_life_indicators_-_productive_or_main_activity#Unemployment_by_age

employees' usually working long hours. From the point of view of elderly people, not excessive hours but low hours of work (or even more the lack of work) seem to be more likely (and potentially problematic). The other subcomponent of 'work-life balance' places the work and care in the focus. It is not unusual for older people to take care of children (or adult persons in need of care) on a regular basis. However, it seems more reasonable to cover this issue in the domain 'social connectedness' than in 'work-life balance'.

Table 4. Labour market attachment and work-life balance

Components and subcomponents	SOCIAL OMC	ACTIVE AGEING INDEX	SCL/PRB INDEX	IPOLIS
<i>Labour market attachment</i>				
Employment	Employment rate of older workers (55-59, 60-64)	Employment rate for the age group 55-59; 60-64; 65-69; 70-74 (EU-LFS)	Percentage of people participating in an economic or social activity (65+)	Employment rate of older workers (55-74) (EU-LFS)
Precarious employment	no	no	no	Involuntary part-time employment as percentage of total part-time employment (55-64) (EU-LFS)
Self-employment	no	no	no	Self-employment as percentage of total employment (55-64) (EU-LFS)
Unemployment	Long term unemployment rate (no age breakdown) (SIP)	no	no	Unemployment rate of older workers (55-64) (EU-LFS)
Labour market attachment of hhs	People living in jobless households (only for those 0-17 and 18-59) (OP)	no	no	less relevant for this module
<i>Work-life balance</i>				
Work and leisure	less relevant for this module			
Work and care	less relevant for this module			

5.3 Indicators of the domain 'Education and training'

Besides its societal benefits, education is a basic determinant of the quality of life of individuals. A lack of skills and competencies limits the access to good jobs and economic prosperity, increases the risk of social exclusion and poverty, and may hinder participation in civic and political affairs¹⁵. In IPOLIS, the domain 'Education and training' consists of two components: 'access to and quality of education' and 'educational achievement'.

¹⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Quality_of_life_indicators_-_education

5.3.1 Access to and quality of education

In what follows, we discuss access to and quality of education, and specifically, the ‘educational attainment’ subcomponent. Educational attainment will be measured using the proportion of elderly people (aged 55 to 74) with upper secondary or tertiary educational attainment. The same measure is included in the Active Ageing Index (see Table 6).

However, to measure the overall level of education one needs data not only on formal education attainment and training, but also on other non-formal educational activities such as adult education and lifelong learning¹⁶. Thus, the other subcomponent is ‘lifelong learning’, which is a highly important policy objective in the EU. The Agenda for New Skills and Jobs, one of the flagship initiatives of Europe 2020, highlights the importance of skills upgrading of older workers who are particularly vulnerable to economic restructuring and policies to support labour market transitions of older people, particularly from unemployment back to work. The Lifelong Learning Programme is highly relevant in this context (European Commission 2012:13). The ‘Education and Training 2020’ strategic framework for European cooperation in education and training, adopted in May 2009, sets a number of benchmarks to be achieved by 2020, including one for lifelong learning. According to this, an average of at least 15% of adults aged 25 to 64 years old should participate in lifelong learning. In the Elderly module of IPOLIS, lifelong learning is assessed by the proportion of those aged 55 to 64 who received education or training in the four weeks preceding the survey (in percentage of the total population of the same age group). The same measure is used for the Active Ageing Index. It should be noted that this is held to be a good measure, but could be improved upon by extending the learning to include more informal training, and by lengthening the period of reference to for example the last six months or last year (Eurostat 2010). The source of data for the indicators of the ‘access to and quality of education’ component is EU-LFS.

5.3.2 Educational achievement

The ‘educational achievement’ component contains one subcomponent being relevant for the elderly: ‘achievement in basic skills’. The ability to use a computer is among the most important competencies, not only for the job market but also to take advantage of education, information and cultural opportunities. ICT skills are among the eight competences, identified by a Recommendation of the European Parliament and of the Council on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning, as most relevant for life and work in a knowledge-based society.¹⁷ Digital competence, as defined by the Recommendation, “... involves the confident and critical use of information Society technology (IST) for work, leisure, learning and communication. It is underpinned by basic skills in ICT: the use of computers to retrieve, access, store, produce, present and exchange information, and to communicate and participate in collaborative networks via the Internet” (ibid). ICT skills are also one of the core 20 indicators for monitoring progress towards the Lisbon objectives in education and training.¹⁸ Furthermore, recognising the crucial role of digital competence in today's society, the European Commission's 2010 Digital Agenda for Europe¹⁹, devoted a whole pillar to digital literacy, skills and inclusion.

The main source of data on internet use is the Community Survey on ICT usage in households and by individuals (ICT). Over many years this survey has developed a broad set of questions and indicators relating to household and individual ICT access, use and skills. Questions on access, use and skills all form parts of the main survey; though, with regard to skills, questions on internet and computer skills are generally rotated – one year computer skills, the following year internet skills

16 http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Quality_of_life_indicators_-_education

17 Recommendation of the European Parliament and of the Council on key competences for lifelong learning; 2006/962/EC

18 Communication from the Commission on a coherent framework of indicators and benchmarks for monitoring progress towards the Lisbon objectives in education and training'; COM(2007) 61 final 21.2.2007

19 Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on A Digital Agenda for Europe; COM(2010) 245 final

(European Commission 2014). Eurostat disseminates data on the level of (basic) computer skills as well as on the level of internet skills. The indicator of computer skills counts individuals having ever carried out at least 3 of the following 6 computer-related activities: coping or moving a file or folder, using copy and paste tools, using basic arithmetic formula in a spreadsheet, compressing (or zipping) files, connecting and installing new devices, writing a computer program using a specialised programming language. Similarly, the indicator of internet skills counts individuals having ever carried out at least 3 of the following 6 internet-related activities: using a search engine to find information, sending e-mails with attached files, posting messages to chatrooms, newsgroups or an online discussion forum, using the internet to make telephone calls, using peer-to-peer file sharing for exchanging movies or music, creating a webpage. Both measures have been chosen as key indicators in the Digital Agenda for Europe scoreboard.²⁰ Beyond the set of indicators measuring the different aspects of digital skills, a current report by the European Commission Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content & Technology presents a proposal for a composite indicator of digital competence, or more exactly, the digital skills indicator, based on four competence areas (information, communication, content creation and problem solving) (European Commission 2014). This is a new development (in a pilot phase at the time of the preparation of this report), and there is no indication on whether this composite indicator will be regularly disseminated.

For building the Elderly module of IPOLIS, we have chosen the indicator on individuals' level of internet skills. This seems to be more informative than computer skills. The indicator is defined as the proportion of older people (55-74) with medium or high level internet skills (i.e. those having ever carried out at least 3 out of the 6 listed internet activities) in percentage of the total population (55-74).

²⁰ http://digital-agenda-data.eu/datasets/digital_agenda_scoreboard_key_indicators/indicators

Table 5. Education and training

Components and subcomponents	SOCIAL OMC	ACTIVE AGEING INDEX	SCL/PRB INDEX	IPOLIS
<i>Access to and quality of education</i>				
Early childhood education	not relevant			
Educational attainment	Persons with low educational attainment (65+)(secondary indicator in SIP)	Percentage of older persons aged 55-74 with upper secondary or tertiary educational attainment (EU-LFS)	no	Percentage of older persons aged 55-74 with upper secondary or tertiary educational attainment (EU-LFS)
Lifelong learning	no	Percentage of older persons aged 55-74 who received education or training in the 4 weeks preceding the survey (EU-LFS)	no	Percentage of older persons aged 55-64 who received education or training in the 4 weeks preceding the survey (EU-LFS)
<i>Educational achievement</i>				
Achievement in basic skills	no	Share of people aged 55-74 using the internet at least once a week (ICT survey)	no	Percentage of older persons aged 55-74 with medium or high level internet skills (ICT)
Early school leaving	not relevant			

5.4 Indicators of the domain ‘Health and risk behaviours’

The domain ‘Health and risk behaviours’ is made up of three components: ‘health status’, ‘health behaviours’ and ‘risk behaviours’. We start the discussion with the ‘health status’ component.

5.4.1 Health status

Health is a major concern for older persons, for it affects one’s ability to care for oneself, to stay active and productive, and to live independently in the community. Poor health directly and indirectly diminishes happiness and overall satisfaction in life (Easterlin 2003).

Healthiness is a complex matter and we need to look at it from various angles in order to present an overall picture. This is the reason why people’s state of health is usually measured using a combination of objective health outcome indicators, subjective perceptions regarding access to healthcare, and self-evaluations of health status. Data on people’s health status are available from different surveys, of which the EHIS and the EU-SILC most deserve to be mentioned. The EHIS provides more nuanced information on older people’s health statuses, while the EU-SILC has the advantage of more frequent periodicity and longer time series. The EU-SILC survey contains a small module on health, composed of three variables on health status and four variables on unmet needs for health care. The variables on health status represent the so called Minimum European Health Module (MEHM), and measures three different concepts of health:

- - self-perceived health;
- - chronic morbidity (people having a long-standing illness or health problem);
- - activity limitation – disability (self-perceived long-standing limitations in usual activities due to health problems).

On the contrary, the EHIS collects a broad set of data on health status. These include data on:

- - limitations in sensorial functions (e.g. vision, hearing);
- - limitations in physical functions (e.g. walking, using one's arms);
- - limitations in Activities of Daily Living (ADL) functions;
- - limitations in Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL) functions.

It should be noted, however, that at the time of completing this report, only 2008 data are available for a limited number of countries.

In order to select the health indicators for the Elderly module of IPOLIS we briefly review the indicators included in the international indices measuring the quality of life of elderly people. They have in common that they all use life expectancy measures. However, the Active Ageing Index relies on more sophisticated measures. These are: the 'remaining life expectancy achievement of 50 years at age 55' and the 'share of healthy life years in the remaining life expectancy at age 55'. The former indicator measures the proportion of life expectancy achievement in the target of 105 years and is calculated as the remaining life expectancy at age 55 divided by 50. The share of healthy life years combines information on quality and quantity of life. It captures the proportion of years spent free of activity limitation in the remaining life expectancy at age 55. The source of both indicators is the European Health and Life Expectancy Information System (EHLEIS).

Nevertheless, health-related indicators are more pronounced in the SCL/PRB Index. Besides life expectancy at older ages, measures of disability, independent living, physical functioning, and of obesity (discussed here in the 'health behaviours' domain) are underlying indicators of the index. 'Disability' is measured using levels of difficulty performing a set of basic daily activities necessary for self-care (ADLs) because of a physical, mental, emotional, or memory problem. Older adults are defined as having no disability if they report no difficulty performing the five ADLs: dressing, bathing, eating, getting in and out of bed, and using the toilet. The 'ability to live independently' is often measured with the ability to perform Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADLs), a set of activities that are generally more complex and require higher levels of physical or mental abilities than those encompassed by ADLs. In the SCL/PRB index, however, 'older people's ability to live independently' is assessed using a single question about taking medication. Finally, 'functional ability' (or physical functioning) is measured with the question on whether one had any difficulty walking for a single city/town block.

People's state of health in the Elderly module of IPOLIS is captured by a combination of objective health outcome indicators and self-evaluations of health status. Accordingly, the 'health' component includes an objective and a subjective health status subcomponent. The 'objective health status' is assessed using four indicators. The first two are 'life expectancy at the age of 65' and 'healthy life years (HLY) at the age of 65'. These indicators are also included in the Health Portfolio of the Social OMC and the former in the ECHI (no. 10) too. Out of the two, the indicator of healthy life years needs some further explanation. This denotes the number of years that a person is expected to continue to live in a healthy condition. A healthy condition is defined as one without limitation in functioning and without disability. The indicator is therefore also called disability-free life expectancy (DFLE). Thus, HLY is a composite indicator that combines mortality data with health status data. The 'objective health status' subcomponent includes additional two indicators based on EU-SILC: the indicator on 'self-perceived limitations in daily activities' and the indicator on 'long-standing illness or health problem'. Both of them are part of the ECHI (no. 35, and no. 34). The indicator on self-perceived limitations in daily activities denotes the percentage of those who answer "yes, strongly limited" or "yes, limited" to EU-SILC question: "For at least the past 6 months, to what extent you have been limited because of a health problem in activities people usually do?" (Answering categories: yes, strongly limited/ yes, limited / no, not limited). Concerning the indicator of self-perceived long-standing limitations we note that since EU-SILC does not cover the institutionalised population who are more likely to face limitations than the population living in private households, this data source

under-estimates the share of the population facing limitations²¹. The indicator on long-standing illness shows the proportion of persons who answer “yes” to question: do you have any longstanding (of a duration of at least six months) illness or health problem?

The ‘subjective health statuses’ of older adults, in accordance with the Social OMC, will be measured with the question on how a person perceives his/her health in general using one of the answering categories very good/ good/ fair/ bad/ very bad. The measure of ‘self-perceived general health’ denotes the percentage of those perceiving their health either bad or very bad. The self-reported general health question is considered as quite reliable (Eurostat 2010: 25). This indicator is derived from EU-SILC.

5.4.2 Health behaviours

The ‘health behaviours’ component consists of two subcomponents: physical activity and obesity. The main source of data on health behaviour is the EHIS. This survey contains a module on health determinants, including questions on height and weight, physical activity as well as on the different forms of risk behaviours.

In the Elderly module of IPOLIS, both subcomponents of ‘health behaviour’ are represented by a single indicator. ‘Physical activity’ is measured using four questions from the EHIS. These ask about the frequency and time of doing vigorous and moderate physical activities in the past seven days. The indicator of ‘practice of daily physical activity among older adults’ is defined as the percentage of the population practising at least 30 minutes of physical activity (moderate or intense) per day. This measure is part of the ECHI system (ECHI no. 52)²².

The other subcomponent is ‘obesity’. Obesity has reached epidemic proportions in many countries and is a major contributor to the global burden of chronic disease and disability. This is not an outcome but a risk factor and has numerous serious health consequences, ranging from increased risk of premature death to serious chronic conditions that reduce the quality of life (Kaneda et al. 2011: 21). The EHIS provides data for calculating the Body Mass Index (BMI), which is used as a basis of identifying obesity. The BMI is defined as the weight in kilos divided by the square of the height in meters. For dissemination purpose, the following subdivision (according to the international obesity taskforce - IOTF) is used:

- underweight: BMI less than 18.5;
- normal weight: BMI between 18.5 and less than 25;
- overweight: BMI between 25 and less than 30;
- obese: BMI equal or greater than 30.

In line with the common definition (also used by the Social OMC), an older adult is considered obese with BMI (derived from the EHIS) equal or greater than 30. The indicator of ‘obesity’ is one of the ECHI indicators on determinants of health (ECHI no. 42).

5.4.3 Risk behaviours

The ‘risk behaviours’ component encompasses six subcomponents of which five are relevant for the Elderly module: smoking, alcohol consumption, illicit drug use, psychological distress and suicide. As can be seen from the summary table (Table 6), the Social OMC includes indicators on regular smoking and alcohol consumption. Indicators of risk behaviours are relatively poorly represented in the SCL/PRB index and the Active Ageing Index. The former uses two measures of risk behaviours:

21 http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Healthy_life_years_statistics

22 http://ec.europa.eu/health/indicators/echi/list/index_en.htm and
http://ec.europa.eu/health/indicators/docs/echi_shortlist_by_policy_area_en.pdf

percent with no report of depression (non-clinical measure) and suicide rate for older adults (reverse coded). In the Active Ageing Index, only the indicator of mental wellbeing is included.

We first discuss the ‘smoking’ subcomponent. In the Elderly module of IPOLIS, smoking behaviour is measured by the indicator of ‘daily smokers’. This indicator is included in the Health Portfolio of the Social OMC and also part of the ECHI (no. 44). The indicator of ‘daily smokers’ is defined as the proportion of older adults reporting to smoke cigarettes (manufactured and hand-rolled) daily. This measure is calculated from answers to the following question from EHIS: ‘Do you smoke at all nowadays?’ The response categories are: Yes, daily / Yes, occasionally / Not at all.

The second subcomponent is ‘alcohol consumption’. Drinking behaviour is a complex phenomenon, and there appears to be no common approach to measuring it. The Health Portfolio provided by the Social OMC contains the indicator of ‘alcohol consumption in litres of pure alcohol per person per year’. This indicator is also part of the ECHI system (no. 46). The Committee on Alcohol Data Collection, Indicators and Definitions, set up by the EC to identify common indicators for use at national and EU level based on existing sources of comparable data, recommended three indicators for monitoring alcohol use and related harm. These are: volume of alcohol consumption measured by total (recorded and unrecorded) yearly consumption of pure alcohol per capita (at age 15 years or older) (ECHI no. 46); pattern of consumption measured by harmful drinking defined as an intake of 60 g of pure alcohol or more on one occasion, monthly or more often, during the previous 12 months (ECHI no. 47); and alcohol-attributable health harm measured by alcohol-attributable years of life lost (European Commission 2010). However, it is important to take into account the differences in drinking behaviour among the different age groups. Research suggests that alcohol consumption generally declines with age and the proportion of non-drinkers increases. The reasons for this decline in consumption are presumably connected to changes in life circumstances and attitudes and, in the later middle aged and older, growing ill health. Despite drinking comparatively little, older drinkers consume alcohol far more often than any other age group.²³ At present, Eurostat disseminates data on the frequency of alcohol consumption and hazardous alcohol consumption (binge drinking), calculated on the basis of the EHIS. In light of the above research findings, we opt for including the indicator of frequency of alcohol consumption in the Elderly module of IPOLIS. (Again, we note that at the time of preparing this report, data are available only for 2008 and for a part of the Member States.) We define the indicator of ‘weekly alcohol consumption’ as the proportion of older adults who consume alcohol at least every week (including those who drink every day).

The next subcomponent of ‘risks behaviour’ is illicit drug use. Data from the EMCDDA show that drug use among the elderly (defined as 55-64 years old) is negligible. In the case of cannabis, the last 12 month prevalence varies from 0 to 0.5 percent in the Member States. Because of the low prevalence throughout the EU, no drug consumption indicator will be included in the Elderly module of IPOLIS.

Mental health of the elderly is difficult to measure. The Active Ageing Index and the SCL/PRB Index use different indicators for assessing the mental well-being of older adults. The former includes the indicator of ‘mental well-being of older population’. This measures self-reported feelings of positive happy moods and spirits. The indicator is based on totalling the raw scores of the five answers to the following questions asked in the EQLS:

- I have felt cheerful and in good spirits;
- I have felt calm and relaxed;
- I have felt active and vigorous;
- I woke up feeling fresh and rested;
- My daily life has been filled with things that interest me.

23 <http://www.ias.org.uk/Alcohol-knowledge-centre/Alcohol-and-older-people.aspx>

As opposed to this, the SCL/PRB Index contains a measure of depression. This is an indicator based on whether or not respondents said they felt depressed much of the time over the week prior to the interview. For the Elderly Module of IPOLIS, we have chosen two indicators: 'psychological distress' and 'psychological well-being of elderly people'. The former indicator is based on five questions included in the EHIS: How much of the time, during the past 4 weeks

- ...have you been very nervous?
- ...have you felt so down in the dumps that nothing could cheer you up?
- ...have you felt calm and peaceful?
- ...have you felt down-hearted and depressed?
- ...have you been happy?

The measure of psychological distress is based on the Mental Health Inventory (MHI-5) which consists of three depression-related items and two anxiety-related items. It has a score of 0 to 100, where a score of 100 represents optimal mental health. The indicator is presented in the form of average score. The measure of psychological distress is part of the ECHI (no. 38). The latter indicator, 'psychological well-being' or Energy and Vitality Index (EVI), is also an ECHI indicator (no. 39) and computed based on the EHIS. This summarizes the answers to the following four questions. How much of the time, during the past 4 weeks

- ... did you feel full of life?
- ...did you have a lot of energy?
- ...did you feel worn out?
- ...did you feel tired?

The indicator is based on the Energy and Vitality Index (EVI) instrument which consists of two vitality-related items and two energy-related items. It has a score of 0 to 100, where a score of 100 represents optimal mental health. The indicator is presented in the form of average score. It has a score of 0 to 100, where a score of 100 represents optimal mental health. The indicator is presented in the form of average score.

Suicide is the last subcomponent of 'risks behaviours'. Suicide is commonly used as a measure of serious mental health problems because most suicide cases meet the criteria for a mental disorder (Kaneda 2011:34). Older people are the group with the highest suicide rates in Europe (Kaneda et al. 2011). Depression, chronic and painful illnesses and social isolation are specific risk factors for suicide in this age group (O'Connell et al. 2004). The cultural and political context for suicides differs across countries and this may affect reporting. A 2006 review of studies on the misclassification of suicides concludes that suicide data in Europe seem to be reliable and that international comparisons may be made over time (Andriessen 2006). However, as a proxy for psychological distress in old age, completed suicides likely represent only the tip of the iceberg (Kaneda et al. 2011). According to a 2010 study by Eurostat, the suicide rate is not appropriate as a measure of mental health for two reasons: firstly, it is an extreme form of mental disorder and many people are mentally ill, without committing suicide, and secondly, there are a lot of data quality problems (registration issues). One can consider including it as an additional analytical variable though. In IPOLIS, we include the suicide death rate as a complementary indicator of mental health.

Table 6. Health and risk behaviours

Components and subcomponents	SOCIAL OMC	ACTIVE AGEING INDEX	SCL/PRB INDEX	IPOLIS
<i>Health status</i>				
Objective health status	Life expectancy at 45, at 65 (HP) Healthy life expectancy at birth, at 45, at 65 (HP) Self-perceived limitations in daily activities (55-64, 65+, 75+)(secondary indicator in HP)(EU-SILC)	Remaining life expectancy achievement of 50 years at age 55 (EHLEIS) Share of healthy life years in the remaining life expectancy at age 55 (EHLEIS)	Life expectancy at older ages (50-54, 65-69, or 75-79 depending on the age group) Percentage of people with no disability (65+) Percentage of people with no difficulty taking medications (living independently) (65+) Percentage of people with no difficulty walking a short distance (no functional limitations)(65+)	Life expectancy at age 65 Healthy life years at age 65 Self-perceived limitations in daily activities (55-84)(EU-SILC) Long-standing illness or health problem (55-84)(EU-SILC)
Subjective health status	Self-perceived general health (55-64, 65+, 75+)(secondary indicator in HP)	no	no	Self-perceived general health: bad and very bad (55-84) (EU-SILC)
<i>Health behaviours</i>				
Physical activity	no	Percentage of population aged 55+ who engage in physical activity and sport at least five times a week (Eurobarometer Special edition 334/2010)	no	Practice of daily physical activity (55-64; 65-74; 75-84) (EHIS)
Obesity	Obesity (55-64, 65+, 75+)(HP)	no	Percentage of people who are not obese (65+)	Share of older people obese (with MBI \geq 30) (55-84) (EHIS)

Components and subcomponents	SOCIAL OMC	ACTIVE AGEING INDEX	SCL/PRB INDEX	IPOLIS
Risk behaviours				
Smoking	Regular smokers (55-64, 65+, 75+)(HP)	no	no	Daily smokers (55-64; 65-74; 75-84) (EHIS)
Alcohol consumption	Alcohol consumption (in litres of pure alcohol per person per year) (55-64, 65+, 75+)(HP)	no	no	Weekly alcohol consumption (55-64; 65-74; 75+) (EHIS)
Illicit drugs	no	no	no	no
Teenage births	not relevant			
Psychological distress	no	Mental well-being of older population aged 55+ (EQLS and WHO's ICD-10)	Percentage of people with no report of depression (non-clinical measure)(65+)	Psychological distress (55-84)(EHIS) Psychological well-being (55-84) (EHIS)
Suicide	no	no	Suicide rate for older adults (reverse coded)(65+)	Suicide rate (65+)

5.5 Indicators of the domain 'Social connectedness and participation'

There are various ways in which social engagement in old age may improve quality of life. Social engagement in old age is associated with better health and greater life satisfaction. Research suggests that being embedded in social networks has a protective influence on physical health. For example, contacts gained from engaging in social activities have well-documented benefits for health, including lower mortality (House et al. 1988). According to Morrow-Howell et al. (2003), older adults who volunteer and who engage in more hours of volunteering report higher levels of well-being. However, there is no effect of the type and the number of organizations for which the older adult volunteer (ibid). The 'social connectedness and civic participation' domain of IPOLIS encompasses relationships with family members and friends as well as group membership and volunteering.

5.5.1 Family and peer relationships

Contact with family and friends is an important way for older adults both to receive and to provide social support. Children typically make up the largest part of one's social support network and provide the main source of informal caregiving in old age. As widely documented, having close relationships with adult children also has a beneficial impact on psychological well-being (see Kaneda et al. 2011 for further details). Both the Active Ageing Index and the SCL/PRB Index use indicators measuring relationships with family members, with special regard to children/grandchildren. The former index includes two family-related indicators: the proportion of those providing care to their children and/or grandchildren and the proportion of those providing care to elderly or disabled relatives. The SCL/PRB index measures family relationships with the proportion of those in contact with at least one child.

Internationally comparable and regular data on people's social connectedness are not abundant. The EQLS seems to be an exception. However, in 2011, a number of changes were made in the

questionnaire affecting the comparability of data on social connectedness across survey waves. In searching for indicators measuring family relationships, it is important to consider these modifications too. For the Elderly module of IPOLIS, we have chosen two indicators on ‘family relationships’. The first is the proportion of older people (65+) living alone. The household composition, though not an outcome-type indicator, is a critical factor for loneliness. Also, we intend to include an indicator on care to children/grandchildren. Unfortunately, the EQLS question on caring for children and grandchildren was modified in 2011, and thus cannot be compared across waves. However, the questionnaire contains items (in a basically unchanged way) on contacts with children (face-to-face or by phone, e-mail or by post). Based on this, we include the indicator on direct (face-to-face) contact with children, defined as the proportion of older people (65+) who have face-to-face contact with children at least once a week.

The ‘peer relationships’ subcomponent can be measured using the EQLS questions on ‘face-to-face contact with friends or neighbours’ and ‘contact with friends or neighbours by phone, e-mail or by post’. Again, we prefer using the question on direct contact. Similarly to the definition of the indicator of relationships with family, the proposed indicator is defined as the share of older people (65+) who have contact with friends or neighbours face-to-face at least once a week.

5.5.2 Civic participation

In IPOLIS, civic participation embraces three subcomponents: voting/voter turnout, group membership and volunteering, and internet use (related to civic participation). Voter turnout is a commonly used measure of civic participation. The ‘voting’ subcomponent includes one single measure: the rate of non-voting. This indicator is the same as the one introduced in the Youth module (Schäfer, Zentarra and Groh-Samberg 2015), based on Hadjar and Beck (2010). The indicator ‘non-voting rate’ is measured by the question: ‘Some people don’t vote nowadays for one reason or another. Did you vote in the last [...] national election?’ in regard to the last election of the primary legislative assembly in ESS. The indicator denotes the proportion of older people (65+) declaring that they did not vote in the last national election. The indicator was dichotomised into the categories ‘No’ (1) and ‘Yes’ (0), thereby omitting all the people who had refused to answer or answered ‘don’t know’ or were ‘Not eligible to vote’. The source of data on voting is the ESS.

The next subcomponent is ‘group membership and volunteering’. Volunteering and participation in community or religious organizations and social clubs are popular ways in which older adults stay socially engaged, especially after they no longer have major life roles as a worker or parent of minor children (Kaneda et al. 2011). In order to promote the social inclusion of the older population, EU policies give special attention to encouraging volunteering. In the context of the European Year of Volunteering in 2011, the EU aims to ‘encourage and support – notably through the exchange of experience and good practices – the efforts of the Community, the Member States, local and regional authorities to create the conditions for civil society conducive to volunteering in the EU and to increase the visibility of voluntary activities in the EU’ (European Commission 2009). Although there is no EU-wide uniform definition of volunteering, the distinction between formal and informal volunteering is used in nearly all Member States to indicate different ways of being engaged in volunteering activities (Eurofound 2010). Formal voluntary work is linked to an organisation outside the private home or the family, such as clubs and associations; informal voluntary work takes, for example, the form of self-help, support within the family or assistance to neighbours (ibid).

Comparable and regular data on ‘group memberships and volunteering’ for the EU Member States are very limited. The ESS and the EQLS provides information on participation in civic and political actions. The ESS question covers seven types of political (and non-political) actions: “During the last 12 months, have you done any of the following? Have you...

- contacted a politician, government or local government official?

- worked in a political party or action group?
- worked in another organisation or association?
- worn or displayed a campaign badge/sticker?
- taken part in a lawful public demonstration?
- signed a petition?
- boycotted certain products?"

The relevant question in the last wave of the EQLS asks respondents whether over the past 12 months, they have...

- attended a meeting of a trade union, a political party or political action group?
- attended a protest or demonstration?
- signed a petition, including an e-mail or on-line petition?
- contacted a politician or public official (other than routine contact arising from use of public services)?

Based on these items, we define an indicator of 'participation in civic and political action'. This informs on the proportion of elderly people (65+) reporting participation in at least one type of civic and political actions in the last 12 months. (This question was asked in the previous, 2007 wave too, but then formulated as a 3-item question, with items 2 and 3 above constituting one item. The above definition of the indicator, however, allows us to compare data across waves.)

The EQLS also ask questions about voluntary work in its 2011/2012 wave. The question refers to unpaid voluntary work through the following organisations in the last 12 months:

- community and social services (e.g. organisations helping the elderly, young people, disabled or other people in need);
- educational, cultural, sports or professional associations;
- social movements (for example environmental, human rights) or charities (for example fundraising, campaigning);
- political parties, trade unions;
- other voluntary organisations.

The answering categories range from 'not at all' to 'every week'. Based on these items, we define an indicator of 'doing unpaid voluntary work' as a share of those people who did voluntary work through any of these organisations at least occasionally over the last 12 months. (The 2007 wave included a much simpler question about voluntary work with different categories of frequency, thus data from the 2011/12 and the previous wave cannot be compared).

The last subcomponent is 'internet use'. Data on internet use are abundant from the ICT survey. Eurostat disseminates data on internet use for a series of different purposes. We have chosen the indicator on 'use of internet for civic and political participation'. Specifically, the ICT survey asks questions on posting opinions on civic or political issues via websites as well as on taking part in on-line consultations and voting. Data on posting opinions are available for 2013, while data on taking part in on-line consultation and voting for 2011 and 2013. We have selected the indicator on 'taking part in on-line consultations or voting' to define civic or political issues.

Table 7. Social connectedness and civic participation

Components and subcomponents	SOCIAL OMC	ACTIVE AGEING INDEX	SCL/PRB INDEX	IPOLIS
<i>Family and peer relationships</i>				
Family relationships	no	Percentage of population aged 55+ providing care to their children and/or grandchildren (at least once a week) (EQLS) Percentage of population aged 55+ providing care to elderly or disabled relatives (at least once a week) (EQLS)	Percentage of people in contact with at least one child (65+)	Proportion of older people (65+) living alone (EU-SILC) Proportion of older people (65+) who have face-to-face contact with children/grandchildren (EQLS)
Peer relationships	no	Percentage of population aged 55+ who meet socially with friends, relatives or colleagues at least once a month (ESS)	no	Proportion of older people (65+) who have face-to-face contact with friends or neighbours (EQLS)
<i>Civic participation</i>				
Voting/Voter turnout	no	no	no	Non-voting (65+)
Group membership/Volunteering	no	Percentage of population aged 55+ taking part in the activities of a trade union/political party/political action group (EQLS) Percentage of population aged 55+ providing unpaid voluntary work through organisations (EQLS)	Percentage of people participating in an economic or social activity (socially connected)(65+)	Proportion of older people (65+) participating in at least one type of civic and political actions (EQLS) Proportion of older people (65+) doing unpaid voluntary work at least occasionally (EQLS)
Internet use	no	no	no	Proportion of those (55-74) using the internet for civic and political participation (ICI)

5.6 Indicators of the domain 'Environmental quality and physical safety'

The last domain of IPOLIS incorporates two components. The first contains indicators on the quality of the local environment, and the second on the safety of the neighbourhood.

5.6.1 Environmental quality

Although, the local environment affects people's quality of life, not much space is devoted to environment quality in the indices measuring quality of life or well-being. From a quality of life perspective self-reporting of the subjectively perceived quality of the environment provides more insight than aggregate overall measurements of pollutants.²⁴ The key sources of information on local environments are EU-SILC and EQLS. EU-SILC asks whether the household's accommodation has "any pollution, grime or other environmental problem caused by traffic or industry". Unfortunately, exposure to air pollution cannot be assessed separately from other environmental problems based on the EU-SILC questions. However, a separate question is asked about noise from neighbours or from the street (of traffic, business, factories, etc.). The questionnaire of EQLS includes a series of possible complaints about the immediate neighbourhood in terms of noise, air pollution, quality of drinking water, crime, violence or vandalism, litter or rubbish on the street, and traffic congestion. Also, there is a question about the access to recreational or green areas. The 'environmental quality' component of IPOLIS uses two indicators: the percentage of elderly people living in households that reported noise from neighbours or from the street, and the percentage of elderly people living in households that reported any pollution, grime or other environmental problem caused by traffic or industry.

5.6.2 Physical safety

Physical safety refers to being protected from any situation that puts a person's physical security at risk, such as crime or accidents. A perceived lack of physical safety may affect subjective well-being more than the actual effects of a physical threat. It is well-known that individual perceptions of crime rates do not always correspond to the actual prevalence of assaults, vandalism and violence. This is one of the reasons why subjective indicators are also needed to complement objective ones²⁵. Questions about crime are asked in EU-SILC, EQLS and ESS. EU-SILC asks about whether respondents (the household reference persons) have experiences of violent crime in the area. The EQLS asks respondents of the question whether they have major/moderate/no problem with crime violence and vandalism. ESS (Round 6) asks people about whether they (or their household members) have been victim of burglary or assault in the last 5 years and whether they feel safe walking alone in their area after dark. To measure physical safety of elderly people we use the above two indicators computed with ESS: 'being victim of burglary/assault in the last 5 years' and 'feeling unsafe walking alone in the area after dark'. The two indicators complement each other: the former one refers to one's experience of victimization (from burglary or assault), while the latter, more subjective one measures fear of crime.

24 http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Quality_of_life_indicators_-_natural_and_living_environment

25 http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Quality_of_life_indicators_-_economic_and_physical_safety

Table 8. Environmental quality and physical safety

Components and subcomponents	SOCIAL OMC	ACTIVE AGEING INDEX	SCL/PRB INDEX	IPOLIS
<i>Environmental quality</i>				
	no	no	no	Noise from neighbours or from the street (EU-SILC) Pollution, grime or other environmental problems (EU-SILC)
<i>Physical safety</i>				
	no	Percentage of population aged 55+ who are not worried about becoming a victim of violent crime (ESS)	no	Being victim of burglary/assault in the last 5 years (ESS) Feeling unsafe walking alone in the local area after dark (ESS)

Table 9. Overview of indicators of the Elderly Module

Name	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage	Overarching
1. MATERIAL LIVING CONDITIONS						
1.1 Poverty						
<i>Extent of poverty</i>						
At-risk-of-poverty after social transfers	Share of elderly people (65+) with an equivalised disposable income (after social transfers) below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60 % of the national median equivalised disposable income after social transfers	a. household type b. sex c. age (65-74; 75+)	EU-SILC	2004-2013		Y
At-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fixed moment in time (2005)	Percentage of elderly people (65+) who are at-risk-of-poverty referring to an at-risk-of-poverty threshold calculated in the standard way for the base year (60% of the 2005 national median equivalised disposable income) and adjusted for inflation only up to the income year considered. Adjustment is based on the annual harmonised index of consumer prices (HICP) of the income reference period.	sex	EU-SILC	2006-2013		Y
<i>Depth of poverty</i>						
Relative median at-risk-of-poverty gap	Difference between the median equivalised disposable income of people below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold and the at-risk-of-poverty threshold, expressed as a percentage of the at-risk-of-poverty threshold.	a. sex b. age (65-74; 75+)	EU-SILC	2004-2013		
<i>Persistency of poverty</i>						
Persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate	Percentage of elderly people (65+) living in households where the equivalised disposable income was below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold for the current year and at least two out of the preceding three years	sex	EU-SILC	2007-2013		Y

1.2 Material deprivation						
Severe material deprivation rate of elderly people	Percentage of elderly people (65+) living in households that cannot afford at least four of the following nine items: 1. to pay their rent, mortgage or utility bills; 2. to keep their home adequately warm; 3. to face unexpected expenses; 4. to eat meat or proteins regularly; 5. to go on holiday; 6. a television set; 7. a washing machine; 8. a car; 9. a telephone.	a. household type b. sex c. age (65-74; 75+)	EU-SILC	2004-2013		Y
Inability to make ends meet	Proportion of elderly people (65+) living in a household with the ability of making ends meet with difficulty or great difficulty.	a. household type b. poverty status	EU-SILC	2004-2013		
1.3 Housing						
<i>Overcrowding</i>						
Overcrowding rate	Percentage of the population living in an overcrowded household. A person is considered as living in an overcrowded household if the household does not have at its disposal a minimum number of rooms equal to: - one room for the household; - one room per couple in the household; - one room for each single person aged 18 or more; - one room per pair of single people of the same gender between 12 and 17 years of age;	a. sex b. poverty status	EU-SILC	2004-2013		Y

	- one room for each single person between 12 and 17 years of age and not included in the previous category; - one room per pair of children under 12 years of age.					
<i>Housing costs</i>						
Housing cost overburden rate	Percentage of the population living in households where the total housing costs ('net' of housing allowances) represent more than 40 % of disposable income ('net' of housing allowances).	a. household type b. sex c. poverty status	EU-SILC	2004-2013		Y
<i>Housing deprivation</i>						
Severe housing deprivation rate	Percentage of population living in the dwelling which is considered as overcrowded, while also exhibiting at least one of the housing deprivation measures. Housing deprivation is a measure of poor amenities and is calculated by referring to those households with a leaking roof, no bath/shower and no indoor toilet, or a dwelling considered too dark.	a. household type b. sex d. poverty status	EU-SILC	2004-2013		Y
1.4 Poverty and social exclusion (EU2020)						
At risk of poverty or social exclusion	Share of the population either (1) at risk of poverty, or (2) severely materially deprived or (3) living in a household with a very low work intensity. The indicator displays the share of people who are at risk of poverty or social exclusion in relation to the total population of the same age group.	a. household type b. sex c. age (65-74; 75+)	EU-SILC	2004-2013		Y
2. LABOUR MARKET ATTACHMENT AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE						
2.1 Labour market attachment						
<i>Employment</i>						
Employment rate	The employment rate is the share of employed persons (55 to 74) in relation to the total population of the same age group.	a. sex	EU-LFS	2004-2014		

			b. age (55-59; 60-64; 65-69; 70-74)				
<i>Precarious employment</i>							
Involuntary employment	part-time	Involuntary part-time employment as percentage of total part-time employment (55-64). Persons working on an involuntary part-time basis are those who declare that they work part-time because they are unable to find full-time work.	sex (no age breakdown because of reliability problems)	EU-LFS	2004-2014		
<i>Self-employment</i>							
Self-employment rate		Self-employment as percentage of total employment (55-64)	a. sex b. age (55-59; 60-64)	EU-LFS	2004-2014		
<i>Unemployment</i>							
Unemployment rate		Number of people (55 to 64) unemployed as a percentage of the labour force (the total number of people employed and unemployed). A person is defined as unemployed if he/she was not employed during the reference week, had actively sought work during the past four weeks and was ready to begin working immediately or within two weeks.	a. sex b. age (55-59; 60-64) c. educational attainment	EU-LFS	2004-2014		
2.2 Work-life balance							
<i>Work and leisure</i>							
<i>Work and care</i>							
3. EDUCATION AND TRAINING							
3.1 Access to and quality of education							
<i>Early childhood education</i>							

<i>Educational attainment</i>						
Having upper secondary or tertiary educational attainment	Percentage of elderly people (55 to 74) with upper secondary or tertiary educational attainment (ISCED 3, 4, 5) http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=edat_lfs_9901&lang=en	sex	EU-LFS	2004-2014	EU-28	
<i>Lifelong learning</i>						
Participation rate in education and training	Percentage of people aged 55 to 64 who received education or training in the four weeks preceding the survey. http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=trng_aes_101&lang=en	a. sex b. educational attainment	EU-LFS	2007, 2011		
3.2 Educational achievement						
<i>Achievement in basic skills</i>						
Medium or high level internet skills (ICT)	Proportion of elderly people (55 to 74) with medium or high level internet skills (i.e. those having ever carried out at least 3 out of the 6 listed internet activities) in percentage of the total population (55-74) http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=isoc_sk_iskl_i&lang=en	sex and age (55-64; 65-74)	ICT	2005-2007, 2010, 2011, 2013		
<i>Early school leaving</i>						
4. HEALTH AND RISK BEHAVIOURS						
4.1 Health status						
<i>Objective health status</i>						
Life expectancy at age 65	The mean number of years that a person of a specific age can expect to live if subjected throughout life to the current mortality conditions (age specific probabilities of dying). http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do	sex	Eurostat	2004-2013		

Healthy life years at age 65 (disability-free life expectancy)	Number of years that a person is expected to live in a healthy condition i.e. the numbers of years of life free of any activity limitation (also called disability-free life expectancy). Based on self-perceived limitations in daily activities. Composite indicator. http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do	sex (the indicator is compiled separately for men and women)	Eurostat	2004-2013		
Self-perceived limitations in daily activities	The percentage sum of people reporting to be limited or strongly limited. http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=hlth_silc_07&lang=en	a. sex b. age (55-64; 65-74; 75-84) c. educational level d. income quintile	EU-SILC	2004-2013		
Long-standing illness or health problem	Proportion of persons who have any longstanding (of a duration of at least six months) illness or longstanding health problem. http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do	a. sex b. age (55-64; 65-74; 75-84) c. educational level d. income quintile	EU-SILC	2004-2013		
<i>Subjective health status</i>						
Self-perceived general health	Percentage sum of people reporting bad or very bad health. http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do	a. sex b. age (55-64; 65-74; 75-84) c. income quintile	EU-SILC	2004-2013		
4.2 Health behaviour						
<i>Physical activity</i>						
Practice of daily physical activity	Percentage of elderly people (55-84) practising at least 30 minutes of physical activity (moderate or intense) per day	a. sex	EHIS	2008 (2006-2009)	in 2008: 11 MSs, from	

	http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=hlth_ehis_de9&lang=en	b. age (55-64; 65-74; 75-84) c. educational attainment		depending on the country), 2014(?)	2014 onwards: EU-28	
<i>Obesity</i>						
Obesity rate	Percentage of elderly people (55-84) who have a BMI equal or greater than 30 in relation to the total population of young people (15-29). http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do	a. sex b. age (55-64; 65-74; 75-84) c. educational attainment	EHIS	2008, 2014(?)	in 2008: 17 MSs, from 2014 onwards: EU-28	
4.3 Risk behaviours						
<i>Smoking</i>						
Daily smokers	Proportion of elderly people (55-84) who smoke cigarettes (manufactured and hand-rolled) daily http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=hlth_ehis_de3&lang=en	a. sex b. age (55-64; 65-74; 75-84) c. educational attainment	EHIS	2008, 2014(?)	in 2008: 16 MSs, from 2014 onwards: EU-28	Y
<i>Alcohol consumption</i>						
Weekly alcohol consumption	Proportion of elderly people (55+) reporting weekly alcohol consumption http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=hlth_ehis_de10&lang=en	a. sex b. age (55-64; 65-74; 75+) c. educational attainment	EHIS	2008, 2014(?)	in 2008: 14 MSs, from 2014 onwards: EU-28	
<i>Illicit drugs</i>						
<i>Teenage births</i>						
<i>Psychological distress</i>						
Psychological distress	The indicator is based on the Mental Health Inventory (MHI-5) which consists of three depression-related items and two anxiety-	a. sex	EHIS	2008, 2014(?)	in 2008: 13 MSs, from	

	related items. It has a score of 0 to 100, where a score of 100 represents optimal mental health. The indicator is presented in the form of average score. http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=hlth_ehis_st7&lang=en	b. age (55-64; 65-74; 75-84) c. educational attainment			2014 onwards: EU-28	
Psychological well-being (energy and vitality index)	The indicator is based on the Energy and Vitality Index (EVI) instrument which consists of two vitality-related items and two energy-related items. It has a score of 0 to 100, where a score of 100 represents optimal mental health. The indicator is presented in the form of average score. http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=hlth_ehis_st8&lang=en	a. sex b. age (55-64; 65-74; 75-84) c. educational attainment	EHIS	2008, 2014(?)	in 2008: 14 MSs, from 2014 onwards: EU-28	
<i>Suicide</i>						
Suicide rate	Crude death rate from suicide and intentional self-harm per 100 000 people	a. sex b. age (60-64; 65-69; 70-74; 75-89; 80-84; 85+)	European detailed mortality database (DMDB) http://data.euro.who.int/dmdb/	2004-2012		
5. SOCIAL CONNECTEDNESS AND PARTICIPATION						
5.1. Family and peer relationships						
<i>Family relationships</i>						
Proportion of older people living alone	Proportion of elderly people (65+) living alone http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=ilc_lvps30&lang=en	sex	EU-SILC	2004-2013	All MSs	

Face-to-face contact with children/grandchildren	Proportion of elderly people (65+) who have face-to-face contact with children/grandchildren at least once a week	a. sex b. age (65-74; 75+)	EQLS			
<i>Peer relationships</i>						
Face-to-face contact with friends or neighbours	Proportion of elderly people (65+) who have face-to-face contact with friends/neighbours at least once a week	a. sex b. age (65-74; 75+)	EQLS			
5.2 Civic participation						
<i>Voting</i>						
Non-voting rate	Proportion of elderly people (65+) declaring that they did not vote in the last national election	a. sex b. age (65-74; 75+)	ESS	2004-2012 in every second year		
<i>Group membership/volunteering</i>						
Participation in civic and political action	Proportion of elderly people (65+) reporting participation in at least one type of civic and political actions in the last 12 months (It should be noted that there was a smaller modification in the items of this question in the 2011 wave, but the definition of the indicator allows us to compare data across waves.)	a. sex b. age (65-74; 75+)	EQLS	2007, 2011		
Doing unpaid voluntary work	Share of elderly people (65+) who did voluntary work through any of the listed organisations at least occasionally over the last 12 months	a. sex b. age (65-74; 75+)	EQLS	2011		
<i>Internet use</i>						
Internet use for civic and political participation	Proportion of elderly people (55-74) taking part in on-line consultations or voting to define civic or political issues http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do	a. sex b. age (65-74; 75+) c. educational attainment	ICT	2011, 2013		

6. ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY AND PHYSICAL SAFETY

6.1 Environmental quality

Noise from neighbours or from the street	Percentage of elderly people (65+) who face the problem of too much noise in their dwelling from neighbours or from outside (traffic, business, factory, etc.)	poverty status	EU-SILC	2004-2013		Y
Pollution, grime or other environmental problems	Percentage of elderly people (65+) who face the problem of pollution, grime or other environmental problems in the local area such as: smoke, dust, unpleasant smells or polluted water.	poverty status	EU-SILC	2004-2013		Y

6.2 Physical safety

Being victim of burglary/assault	Percentage of those (65+) who (or any of his/her household members) have been victim of burglary or assault in the last 5 years.	a. sex b. age (65-74; 75+)	ESS	2004-2012 in every second year	the number of countries varies from wave to wave	
Feeling unsafe walking alone after dark	Percentage of those (65+) who feel unsafe/very unsafe walking alone in the local area after dark	a. sex b. age (65-74; 75+)	ESS	2004-2012 in every second year	the number of countries varies from wave to wave	

6. Recommendations for improving the monitoring of older people's quality of life

A significant improvement in monitoring the situation of the most vulnerable has taken place over the past decades in Europe, due to better coordination, in-depth research and an improved data infrastructure. Setting up the Elderly module of the IPOLIS, however, revealed some shortcomings of this monitoring system. In what follows, we summarize our main findings and make some recommendations for further improvements in the measurement of older people's quality of life.

In the selection of indicators for the Elderly module of IPOLIS, we used surveys conducted in the total population. We could not use the only survey of older adults (50+), SHARE, because of its relatively poor country coverage. As was seen, EU-SILC and EU-LFS served as the main data sources for the Elderly module of IPOLIS. Indicators for the domains 'Material living conditions' and 'Environmental quality and physical safety' were derived from EU-SILC, while indicators for 'Labour market attachment and work-life balance' and 'Education and training' from the EU-LFS. Besides these data sources, EQLS provides data for the domain 'Social connectedness and civic participation'. EHIS is the main source of data in regard to the domain 'Health and risk behaviour'. However, it is important to stress that EHIS data for all MSs will be available only from the current round onwards. Finally, some indicators were derived from the ESS and the ICT.

6.1 Encouraging the extension of monitoring of older people in terms of quality of life domains and components

When building the Elderly module of IPOLIS, we found that there is a large pool of policy relevant, timely, cross-country comparable and robust indicators in regard to some quality of life domains (e.g. 'Material living conditions' and 'Health and risk behaviours'). In the case of some other domains (e.g. 'Social connectedness and civic participation' and 'Environmental quality and physical safety'), the indicator coverage and the data infrastructure seem to be poorer. For all domains, however, smaller or larger gaps can be identified and thus the monitoring of older people's quality of life can be improved. In what follows we make recommendations regarding the indicators as well as the underlying data infrastructure. The recommendations are listed by domains of QoL.

1. Material living conditions

Our recommendations are related to the components of 'Material deprivation' and 'Housing'. According to research findings, measures of material deprivation appear to work less well for the older age group (than for families with children) (McKay 2008, Guio et al. 2012). For example, some of the items being asked about appear to be less relevant for the older age group (McKay 2008, Guio et al. 2012). In addition, older people are less likely to say they cannot afford an item they lack, and more likely to say they do not want it (McKay 2004, Guio et al. 2012). These findings might suggest that further work is needed on this issue, potentially including the development of age-specific indicators for measuring material deprivation.

Some of the regular indicators measuring housing conditions are less relevant for older people than for the other vulnerable age groups (e.g. overcrowding and severe housing deprivation). On the other hand, there is a need of specific indicators for measuring housing conditions of older people. One such is physical accessibility of basic services (e.g. public transport, food shop, etc.),

which is essential for the elderly to live an independent life and actively participate in society. Currently, we lack such regular indicators and the underlying data. Although, the special Housing module of EU-SILC 2007 contained a couple of questions about the accessibility of public transport, grocery services, primary health care services, etc., these have not become part of the core questionnaire.

2. Education and training

Lifelong learning, a subcomponent of ‘access to and quality of education’ is of key importance for the old age group. This is measured by the proportion of those (aged 55 to 64) who received education or training in the four weeks preceding the survey. The indicator is derived from EU-LFS. We support the recommendation made by Eurostat (2010) that this measure should be improved upon by extending the learning to include more informal training, and by lengthening the period of reference to the last six months or last year.

3. Social connectedness and civic participation

The ‘Social connectedness and civic participation’ domain of IPOLIS encompasses relationships with family members and friends as well as different forms of civic participation: voting, group membership and volunteering, and internet use for civic participation. Indicators and the underlying data are missing or inappropriate in regard to relationships with family members (especially care provided to children/grandchildren or to the elderly or disabled relatives) and relationships with friends. The main data source for these indicators is the EQLS. This survey asks questions on social connections but data cannot always be compared across waves due to modifications in the questionnaire (e.g. questions on care to children/grandchildren and care to elderly or disabled relatives or questions on participation in civic and political actions). Another problem with EQLS and with other surveys of total population is that the size of the elderly subsample may be too small to provide breakdowns by socio-demographic variables.

4. Environmental quality and physical safety

This is probably the domain we know the least about, especially the ‘environmental quality’ component. The key sources of information on local environments are EU-SILC and EQLS. Both surveys have their own weaknesses. Exposure to air pollution cannot be assessed separately from other environmental problems based on the EU-SILC questions. At the same time, the EQLS asks about a series of environmental complaints, and even includes a question about the access to recreational or green areas. However, in some cases, there are modifications in the questions from wave to wave.

6.2 Extending the monitoring of older people to the “oldest old”

The EU-SILC covers the population living in private households, while a significant part of the “oldest old” lives in communal establishments (e.g. old-age homes, long term care facilities, etc.). There are at least two problems arising from this. Firstly, this may lead to biased estimates of indicators, depending on the share of those living in communal settings and on the differences in the main socio-demographic characteristics of those living in private households and communal establishments. Therefore, we propose an in-depth cross-country analysis on how and to what extent indicator estimates for older people based on such surveys are biased due to the fact that the probability of living in a communal establishment is increasing with age. We suggest disseminating data derived from the EU-SILC (and other surveys sampled on private households) with an upper age limit of 85. Secondly, no cross-country information is available on the quality of life of institutionalized elderly people. We recommend that the monitoring of older people should be extended to those living in communal establishments.

6.3 Supporting Member States to participate in SHARE to promote full country coverage in certain QoL domains

As was already mentioned, SHARE would be an appropriate source of information in some domains (e.g. social and family networks), but it provides data far not for all Member States. Therefore, we recommend that the European Commission encourage and support Member States to participate in SHARE. The use of SHARE for monitoring the quality of life of older people instead of total population surveys would allow providing breakdowns by socio-demographic variables. Also, the full country coverage would greatly contribute to better monitoring of EU policies in relation to the elderly.

6.4 Supporting the harmonisation of data infrastructure regarding the QoL of older people

Finally, we recommend that a task force should be established to ensure that the requirements defined for the measures of a particular indicator system are fully met. These are: the indicators should be timely and regular. The latter requirement also means that it is important that the content of the indicator be constant in time (e.g. in the case of some EQLS questions, as mentioned above), and certain questions included in ad-hoc modules of EU-SILC be part of the monitoring system (e.g. the above questions in the Housing module should be part of the core questionnaire). Full coverage of Member States is another important criterion. Finally, the harmonisation of the socio-economic characteristics of individuals and households across surveys would also contribute to a better monitoring of the quality of life of the elderly.

References

- Abdallah, S. and Stoll, L. (2012). Review of individual-level drivers of subjective well-being, produced as part of the contract 'Analysis, implementation and dissemination of well-being indicators', Eurostat.
- Andriessen, K. (2006). "Do we need to be cautious in evaluating suicide statistics?" *European Journal of Public Health*, 16(4):445–447.
- Berk, L. E. (2013). *Development through the Life Span*. Allyn & Bacon, 6th Edition
- Easterlin, R.A. (2003). "Explaining Happiness." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 100(19): 11176-83.
- Eurofound (2010). *Measures for social inclusion of the elderly: The case of volunteering*. Working Paper
- European Commission (2009). Proposal for a Council Decision on the European Year of Volunteering (2011), COM(2009) 254 final, Brussels Available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32010D0037&from=EN>
- European Commission (2010). 'EUROPE 2020 A Strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth', Brussels, 3.3.2010 COM (2010) 2020 Final. Available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2010:2020:FIN:EN:PDF>
- European Commission (2011). *Progress towards the common European objectives in education and training (2010/2011). Indicators and benchmarks*. Commission staff working document Brussels, 18.04.2011 SEC(2011) 526 final. Available at: <http://edz.bib.uni-mannheim.de/edz/pdf/sek/2011/sek-2011-0526-1-en.pdf>
- European Commission (2012). *The EU Contribution to Active Ageing and Solidarity between Generations*
- European Commission Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content & Technology (2014). *Measuring Digital Skills across the EU: EU wide indicators of Digital Competence*. May 2014. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/measuring-digital-skills-across-eu-eu-wide-indicators-digital-competence>
- European Commission Eurostat (2010). *EHIS indicators guidelines*. List of indicators to be computed with the EHIS. Last update 24 November 2010. Available at: <https://circabc.europa.eu/d/d/workspace/SpacesStore/d4c9d574-8658-4c21-9cf2-04768b38afe8/EHIS%20indicators%20quidelines%20-%20final%20version.pdf>
- Council of the European Union (2012). 'Council Declaration on the European Year for Active Ageing and Solidarity between Generations (2012): The Way Forward', 17468/12, SOC 992, SAN 322. Available at: <http://europa.eu/ey2012/BlobServlet?docId=9231&langId=en>
- EUROSTAT (2011). 'Active ageing and solidarity between generations – A statistical portrait of the European Union 2012', Eurostat Statistical Books, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3217494/5740649/KS-EP-11-001-EN.PDF/1f0b25f8-3c86-4f40-9376-c737b54c5fcf>
- Eurostat (2010). *Feasibility Study for Well-being Indicators – Task 4: critical review*. Technical Report, available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/118025/118135/Feasibility_study_Well-Being_Indicators.pdf/2475816b-9e4f-44e4-9ebf-2cd05762df77

- Fudge, J; and R. Owens (2006). "Precarious work, women and the new economy: the challenge to legal norms". In Fudge, J; R. Owens. *Precarious work, women and the new economy: the challenge to legal norms*. Onati International Series in Law and Society. Oxford: Hart Publishing. pp. 3–28.
- Fudge, J, E. Tucker, and L. Vosko (2002). The legal concept of employment: Marginalizing workers. Report for the Law Commission of Canada, Ottawa.
- Gábos, A. and M. Kopasz (2014). Concept paper for an integrated poverty and living conditions indicator system (IPOLIS) database. Deliverable under the Poverty pillar of the InGRID project. Available at: <http://inclusivegrowth.be/downloads/output/d20-1-ipolis-concept-paper.pdf>
- Gábos, A. and M. Kopasz (2015). Methodological and data infrastructure report on children. Budapest, InGRID. Available at: <http://inclusivegrowth.be/downloads/output/ms20-6-mdir-on-children-eind.pdf>
- Guio, A.-C., D. Gordon and E. Marlier (2012). Measuring material deprivation in the EU: Indicators for the whole population and child-specific indicators, Eurostat Methodologies and working papers, Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities (OPOCE).
- Hadjar, A. and M. Beck (2010): Who does not participate in elections in Europe and why is this? *European Societies*, 12:4, 521-542, DOI:10.1080/14616696.2010.483007).
- Hatfield, I. (2015). Self-employment in Europe. IPPR, January 2015
- House, J.S., K.R. Landis, and D. Umberson (1988). "Social Relationships and Health." *Science* 24(1): 540-45.
- Kaneda, T, M. Lee, and K. Pollard, K. (2011). 'SCL/PRB Index of Well-Being in Older Populations - Final Report Global Ageing and Monitoring Project', Washington DC: Population Reference Bureau.
- McKay, S., S. Jefferys, A. Paraksevopoulou, J. Keles (2012). "Study on Precarious work and social rights". Working Lives Research Institute, [London Metropolitan University](http://www.met.ac.uk), European Commission
- McKay, S. (2008). Measuring material deprivation among older people: Methodological study to revise the Family Resources Survey questions. Department for Work and Pensions Working Paper Number 54. Available at: <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/poverty/downloads/keyofficialdocuments/FRS%20Older%20people%20deprivation%20questions%20report.pdf>
- McKay, S. (2004). 'Poverty or preference: What do 'consensual deprivation indicators' really measure?' *Fiscal Studies*, June, vol. 25 (2) pp. 201-223, London: Institute for Fiscal Studies.
- Morrow-Howell, N, J. Hinterlong, P.A. Rozario, and F. Tang. (2003). "Effects of Volunteering on the Well-Being of Older Adults." *Journals of Gerontology, Series B: Psychological Sciences and Social Sciences* 58: S137-145.
- O'Connell, H., A. Chin, C. Cunningham, and B.A. Lawlor (2004). "Recent developments: Suicide in older people." *BMJ*. 329(7444):895-899. Available at: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC523116/>
- Sanderson, W.C. and S. Scherbov (2008). Rethinking Age and Aging. *Population Bulletin* Vol. 63, No.4
- Schäfer, A., A. Zentarra and O. Groh-Samberg (2015). Methodological and data infrastructure report on the youth. Bremen, InGRID.
- Tomassini, C., K. Glaser, D.A. Wolf, M.I. Broese van Groenou, E. Grundy (2004). Living arrangements among older people: an overview of trends in Europe and the USA. *Popul Trends*. Spring;(115):24-34.
- Torpy, J.M. (2006). Frailty in older adults. *The Journal of the American Medical Association*, 296(18), 2280.

- UNECE (2012a). 'Active Ageing', UNECE Policy Brief on Ageing No. 13, June 2012, United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, Geneva. Available at: http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/pau/age/Policy_briefs/ECE-WG.1.17.pdf
- UNECE (2012b). 'Active Ageing and Quality of Life In Old Age', Report prepared by Clemens Tesch-Roemer of German Centre of Gerontology, ECE/WG.1/16, United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, Geneva. Available at: <http://www.unece.org/index.php?id=30027>
- UNFPA (2012) Ageing in the Twenty-First Century: A Celebration and A Challenge
- WHO Regional Office for Europe (2012). Alcohol in the European Union Consumption, harm and policy approaches. Available at: http://www.euro.who.int/__data/assets/pdf_file/0003/160680/e96457.pdf
- Zaidi, A., K. Gasior, M. M. Hofmarcher, O. Lelkes, B. Marin, R. Rodrigues, A. Schmidt, P. Vanhuyse and E. Zolyomi (2013). "Active Ageing Index 2012: Concept, Methodology and First Results" EC/UNECE, Active Ageing Index Project, UNECE Grant ECE/GC/2012/003, European Centre for Social Welfare Policy and Research, Vienna, March 2013.
- Zizza, C. A.; K.J. Ellison; and C.M. Wernette (2009). "Total Water Intakes of Community-Living Middle-Old and Oldest-Old Adults". *The Journals of Gerontology Series A: Biological Sciences and Medical Sciences* 64A (4): 481. Available at: <http://biomedgerontology.oxfordjournals.org/content/64A/4/481.full.pdf+html>

InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

InGRID is supported by the European Union’s Seventh Programme for Research, Technological Development and Demonstration under Grant Agreement No 312691.

More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

Co-ordinator

Guy Van Gyes
Monique Ramioul

Partners

TÁRKI Social Research Institute Inc. (HU)
Amsterdam Institute for Advanced labour Studies, Universiteit van Amsterdam (NL)
The Swedish Institute for Social Research, Stockholms Universitet (SE)
Fachbereich IV, Wirtschafts- und Sozialstatistik, Universität Trier (DE)
Centre d'Etudis Demogràfics, Campus de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (ES)
Centre d'Etudes de Population, de Pauvreté et de Politiques Socio-Economiques (LU)
Centre for Social Policy, Universiteit Antwerpen (BE)
Institute for Social & Economic Research, University of Essex (UK)
Bremen International Graduate School of Social Sciences, Universität Bremen (DE)
Department of Dynamics of Organisations of Work, Centre d'Etudes de l'Emploi (FR)
The Centre for European Policy Studies (BE)
Dipartimento di Economica e Management, Università di Pisa (IT)
Social Statistics Division, University of Southampton (UK)
Luxembourg Income Study, asbl (LU)
WageIndicator Foundation (NL)
School of Social Sciences, The University of Manchester (UK)

InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research
Infrastructure Diffusion
Contract No 312691

For further information about
the InGRID project, please contact
inclusive.growth@kuleuven.be
www.inclusivegrowth.be
p/a HIVA – Research Institute
for Work and Society
Parkstraat 47 box 5300
3000 Leuven
Belgium